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CONTACT

E-mail: contact@ijerresearch.org

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THIRST

Av. Pastor Martin Luther King
Júnior, 126 (Torre 2000 Sala 104)
Del Castilho
Rio de Janeiro - RJ - Brasil
CEP 20765-971
TEL: +55 (21) 3490-5511

FOR SUBMISSION OF ARTICLES
E-mail: editor@ijerresearch.org

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University of Goiás (UEG).

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SUMMARY

- 07** CLASSROOM MANAGEMENT AFTER THE PANDEMIC CRISIS IN THE MUNICIPAL SCHOOL SYSTEM OF THE CITY OF SÃO PAULO
- GlauCIA Aparecida de Oliveira: glauciaaparece@gmail.com
- 19** COGNITIVE DEVELOPMENT OF AUTIST STUDENTS: A CASE STUDY ABOUT THE SUPPORT TEACHER AT COLÉGIO ESTADUAL DE GOIATUBA (GO)
-Elismárcia Luiz Moura Santos.
- 25** CONTENT ANALYSIS OF THE SOCIAL REPRESENTATION IN THE NARRATIVES OF CHRONIC PATIENTS
- Camila Rodrigues Rodrigues (profcamilacristinarodrigues@gmail.com) and Ricardo De Bonis (ricardo@debonis.com.br).
- 31** DEMOCRATIC MANAGEMENT AND THE SPECIFICITY OF THE SCHOOL FOR ADOLESCENTS IN COMPLIANCE WITH A SOCIO-EDUCATIONAL MEASURE
- Paula Rosangela Gonçalves da Costa and Benedita Augusta Ferreira Furtado.
- 42** PSYCHO-PEDAGOGICAL INTERVENTION: STUDY DEVELOPED AT THE FRANCISCAN HIGHER EDUCATION INSTITUTE OF PAÇO DO LUMIAR, MA-
-Lizilene Araújo Neves Saldanha
- 52** STUDY ON THE SUSTAINABILITY AND MANAGEMENT OF MANAGEMENT OF SMALL HOTELS: IN RELATION TO THE ENVIRONMENT IN CALDAS NOVAS (GO), FROM 2015 TO 2020
-Ronaldo do Nascimento Carvalho and Joana D'arc Bardella Castro.

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CLASSROOM MANAGEMENT AFTER THE PANDEMIC CRISIS IN THE MUNICIPAL SCHOOL SYSTEM OF THE CITY OF SÃO PAULO

AUTHORS

Glauca Aparecida de Oliveira: Master in Educational Sciences. Specialist in Educommunication, Educational Guidance and Psychopedagogy. Graduated in Literature, Pedagogy and History. Teacher since 1997 at the São Paulo Municipal Education Network.

ABSTRACT

The lack of initial teacher training in the development of strategies to promote collaborative human relationships has genuine opportunities in the continuing training of collective teacher study hours to deconstruct inadequate conceptions, develop cooperative practices and give new meaning to one's own experiences. Having overcome adversities directly linked to the acute phase of the Covid-19 pandemic, I have identified four dimensions that are essential to professional practice today: managing anxieties and uncertainties, devising viable strategies for this new context, improving collective collaborative work and managing relationships in the online and face-to-face environment. The aim of this article is to contextualize the importance of building learning through the exercise of students' protagonism, autonomy and determination, given in the dialogue between them and the teacher, in a multi-way learning process with competent mediation. Using the social experiences of the group of students as clues for selecting approaches, content and strategies makes it possible to add meaning for them. Welcoming the vision of the local community into the classroom as a safe starting point enables teaching that is less content-oriented and more focused on comprehensive education (WEISZ, 2009), as well as the use of resources that enable authorial and collaborative production.

Keywords: education; learning; teacher training; didactics; teaching practice

INTRODUCTION

The anguish of discovering that the details of a classroom routine went far beyond the annual planning and preparation of an activity, or any lesson for that matter, highlighted my poor initial teacher training in developing strategies to promote collaborative human relationships. However, the determination to overcome such discomfort and frustration served as fuel for the search for alternatives that, while alleviating the suffering of the uncertainties of the teaching and learning process, would also provide successful experiences for the students.

I found genuine opportunities to deconstruct inadequate conceptions, develop cooperative practices and give new meaning to my experiences as a student and daughter of a public school teacher, experiences permeated by the specificities of black, poor and peripheral women, like my mother and me.

Currently, having overcome adversities directly linked to the acute phase of the Covid-19 pandemic, a historical and atypical planetary moment, in which social distancing and the demands of remote teaching have led me to reflect on my teaching training path, I identify four dimensions that are indispensable to my professional performance today: the management of anxieties and uncertainties, the elaboration of viable strategies for this new context, the improvement in collaborative collective work and the management of relationships in the online and face-to-face environment.

DEVELOPMENT

Reflecting on the functioning of the Brazilian school system prior to the Law of Guidelines and Bases of National Education No. 9394/96 (BRASIL, 1996), and its amendment via Law No. 10639/2003 - which instituted in the official curriculum the compulsory presence of the theme "Afro-Brazilian and African History and Culture" (BRASIL, 2003) - was the foundation of the continuing education that favored my awareness in welcoming the expectations of boys and girls in the classroom.

The laws and decrees of the colonial and imperial periods did not make significant investments and

efforts to educate the entire population. The 1824 Constitution of Empire Brazil declared that primary education was free for all Brazilian citizens, but excluded enslaved black people from citizenship. Thus, since they were prohibited by the state from having access to school, "the 1872 census revealed that among 1,509,403 enslaved people, only 1,403 knew how to read and write, in other words, less than 1%. The access and integration of the enslaved into society was blocked, preventing them from facing the new challenges of the free wage labor market" (SÃO PAULO, 2008, p.67).

Although paid for by everyone's taxes, in the 1960s we found public schools that were still segregated, neglecting black students and repeatedly promoting the threat of failure as the only way to force children and teenagers to study; a public school that, not built for everyone, required passing competitive entrance exams, blocking and discouraging a significant portion of the student population, especially the most precarious in terms of their financial situation and the establishment of study routines (Weisz, 2009). Child labor, women's role as caretakers of the home and family, and the country's slave-owning past are some of the factors that determined why almost entire segments of society were prevented from accessing school or coerced into dropping out (SÃO PAULO, 2008).

With the 1971 LDB, the separation between primary and secondary schools was eliminated, the entrance exam was abolished and education up to the 8th grade became compulsory. The educational policy aimed to guarantee access to school for the entire population, but the educational system did not direct its strategies towards guaranteeing learning and progression (WEISZ, 2009).

The state, despite being a benefactor in providing a wide range of enrollments, was complicit in maintaining the culture of failure as the only device capable of ensuring quality education, failing to invest in public policies and teacher training that would guarantee adequate teaching and learning processes with equity. In other words, making it possible to access education as a human right, meeting the needs, differences and asymmetries of the various social segments (CHAUÍ, 1995).

So we have compulsory schooling, but far from this meaning that it is for everyone. Government policies

still persist today that are impregnated with this elitist vision of education that is structurally hierarchical and authoritarian, “preserving the marks of colonial slave society” (CHAUI, 1995, p. 74). Weisz (2009) observes that in this scenario, historically characterized by this exclusionary and meritocratic interpretation, the belief that school failure had its origins in malnutrition gained momentum, leading successive governments to expand school lunch programs. Although the importance of healthy eating for the development of life is unquestionable, the use of school feeding policies has not resulted in overcoming educational failure.

Class stereotypes and prejudices, cultivated during successive centuries of denial of the right to humanity, dignity, citizenship and subjectivity, have produced school failure in the daily life of hierarchical and authoritarian relationships in school spaces. Patto (1987) argues that, precisely because of the influence of personal and family history on the trajectory of schooling in Brazilian society, school failure is a psychosocial process, in which students are stigmatized because of their ethnic heritage, social and cultural conditions.

According to Weisz (2009), it was the understanding of the economic role of education in the country's development that fundamentally changed the way Brazilian society looked at the issue of education. The growing concern with citizenship issues, fostered by social participation, put pressure on Brazilian elites to realize that the traditional exclusion of large population groups from access to basic social welfare conditions would turn against them in two ways: companies needed a consumer market to become more competitive, including abroad, and repeated processes of exclusion would eventually fuel population uprisings.

After an intense process of debate, seeking to reconcile the interests of the various groups representing society, in 1996 the National Congress decreed a new National Education Guidelines and Bases Law (BRASIL, 1996).

At that time, I began my career having contact with colleagues who were confused about how to

reconcile the ideas of universal access to school and making continuous progression within cycles real in the classroom, guaranteeing learning (Weisz, 2009).

In the collective teaching study hours, we clashed with our cultural beliefs countless times, reading texts that intended to expose the tricks of exclusion established in the network of human relationships that are the foundation of this country and, at the same time, deconstruct our conceptions of students, teachers and assessment. Also at the end of the 1990s, the Ministry of Education and Culture's (MEC) program offered a methodological reference for in-service teacher training. Called PCN em Ação (PCN in Action), it helped to understand the theoretical frameworks of the Parâmetros Curriculares Nacionais (BRASIL, 1999) - the aforementioned PCNs - institutional documents with recommendations on curriculum, drawn up between 1995 and 1998. With national reach, other actions by the MEC addressed the difficulty teachers had with literacy, producing a specific program to train literacy teachers, known as PROFA. This project consisted of offering a permanent training course, based on respect for the group's knowledge and problem-solving methodologies, written and videographic materials. I was studying for a degree in Languages and Literature and both the teachers from the academy and those who worked with me in the Municipal Education Network of the City of São Paulo (RME) were promoting discussions about developing educational practices that were different from what had been commonly done in the classroom until then.

In 2006, the Municipal Department of Education of the City of São Paulo (SME/SP) implemented the Ler e Escrever Program which, in addition to providing the Literacy Teacher's Planning Guide, was structured around the ongoing training of pedagogical coordinators (PC) - together with the Technical Guidance Department of the Municipal Department of Education (DOT/SME). The PTs had the task of organizing collective working hours with the teachers and monitoring their pedagogical activities (SÃO PAULO, 2006a).

Expanding the reference material for teacher

improvement, 2007 saw the publication of the document *Orientações Curriculares e Proposição de Expectativas de Aprendizagem* (2007), which was part of the Programa de Orientação Curricular do Ensino Fundamental (Elementary School Curriculum Orientation Program), with the aim of contributing to reflection and discussion in the process of selecting and organizing content.

The document was drawn up based on contributions from specialists in the areas of knowledge and coordinated by the DOT/SME, followed by reading by groups of teachers, supervisors and representatives of the Education Coordinating Offices for the necessary adjustments. This was followed by the curricular reorientation stage, which sought to link the document to the results of external assessments in order to draw up teaching plans that were appropriate to the students' learning needs, prioritizing the provision of social reading and writing practices. The documents *Orientações Curriculares do Ensino Fundamental I*, *Orientações Curriculares do Ensino Fundamental II* (for the areas of knowledge) and the *Referencial de Expectativas para o Desenvolvimento da Competência Leitora e Escritora no Ciclo II do Ensino Fundamental* (2006b) present the term "learning expectations" as development goals, i.e. competences and skills that expand as they are achieved and progressively deepened, in line with the students' development process.

For sometime now, I have been assigned exclusively to the classes as a Reading Room Guidance Teacher (POSL), and I have seen various practices and routines already consolidated by the "reading teachers" (as POSLs are commonly known in the school community) officially recorded in the aforementioned collection. With no obligation to record grades or concepts, the work carried out in the Reading Rooms and Reading Spaces has the primary objective (SÃO PAULO, 2019):

to awaken students' interest in reading, through the experience of various situations in which its use is necessary, and through interaction with published materials from the most diverse literary genres and media, enhancing the

development of reading behavior.

Investing in strategies, time, care and affection in the development of reading behavior (in the most diverse classes, with conflicting profiles and careful preferences) requires POSL professionals to be constantly updated and to have a keen sense of how to involve students who are sometimes disrespected in their right to comprehensive learning.

In this project, the content includes not only objective strategies for the acquisition of students' reading and writing skills, but also strategies that promote self-knowledge and self-care, the improvement of autonomy and determination, conflict mediation, and the management of anxieties and uncertainties. These strategies, which were then organized and documented, became accessible and, above all, indispensable in text production and reading comprehension practices, that is, in the social use of reading and writing in all areas of knowledge (SÃO PAULO, 2006).

In my experience with children, teenagers, young people and adults in the different dynamics of the Reading Room, I met students who were involved in the activities on offer, even though they had a history of low academic performance and indiscipline. My strategies for managing my anxieties, difficulties and uncertainties often also became content, alongside the strategies exemplified by the students themselves and other teachers.

Even more dissatisfied with the lack of progress of some students in regular classes and devoting special attention to trying to understand what was preventing children and adolescents from learning, in 2016 I accepted the proposal to join the Pedagogical Support Project - Parallel Recovery (PAP), starting to attend small classes in the after-school hours in learning recovery workshops.

The PAP's ongoing training is based on the Learning Rights related to the Social Quality of Education. The institutional publication *Learning Rights in the Interdisciplinary and Authorial*

Cycles (2016), emphasized learning as a human right, reflecting the curricular movement National Pact for Literacy at the Right Age (PNAIC) (collaborative agreement signed between the Federal Government, Federal District, States and Municipalities in 2012, to make literacy effective for all children by the end of the 3rd year of elementary school at the latest) (BRASIL, 2017).

In the process of implementing the São Paulo City Curriculum, in 2016 a collection of guiding documents was produced through data collection, action and discussions fostered in working groups (WG), which involved the representation of various segments of the municipal school community. With integral education, equity and inclusive education as their guiding concepts, these collective productions currently make up a collection for the continuing education of RME professionals, as well as being freely accessible to society. In particular, the collection Didactic Guidelines for the City Curriculum brings together relevant notes and suggestions so that planning can find its full functionality in the teaching and learning process, especially in everyday classroom work.

I didn't find in any of these publications, most of which were produced with the collaboration of professionals from the public education system, any justification for school failure based on the family, the one that doesn't stimulate, feed or take proper care of their babies, children and adolescents, although the common justification for low school performance is still concentrated in families in the most precarious situations.

In the classrooms, in the reading circles and in the PAP workshops, I met a number of girls and boys who were restless and questioning, rebellious and savvy, whose way of being and existing in the world caused discomfort and sometimes broke with the school plan. It's human and perfectly acceptable that failure to comply with a plan can cause anguish, but there are ways to make the process of realigning the path part of the plan's success. Pedagogical work requires planning, knowledge, very sharp criteria and intentionality, precisely because of the need to manage the most

uncertainties and anxieties. However, they are natural and permanent in human existence and are also sources of learning (PASCUAL, 2020).

In times of pandemic, the classroom, whether remote or face-to-face, has been a meeting of people full of feelings - some of them not even named yet - and experiences, many of them still far from being re-signified. Lesson planning that also considers dialog about feelings as part of the systematic content, either as a pretext or as an in-depth study of the previously listed theme, is in line with the practice of competencies described in the National Common Curriculum Base (BNCC) and in UNESCO's proposal for Education for Sustainable Development (ESD).

At the beginning of March 2020, we were at school during our collective study time, reflecting on the correspondence between the ESD key competences and the Matriz de Saberes do Currículo da Cidade de São Paulo. That day we read (SÃO PAULO, 2019B, p. 37):

A curriculum designed today needs to dialogue with the dynamics and dilemmas of contemporary society, so that new generations can actively participate in the positive transformation of both their local reality and global challenges.

Well, today the disturbing reality is the favorable state of opportunities for effective work based on this curriculum, enabling the formation "of ethical, responsible and supportive citizens who strengthen a more inclusive, democratic, prosperous and sustainable society" (SÃO PAULO, 2019B, p.35). Self-knowledge and self-care can be experienced through activities, games or dynamics that promote reports of personal impressions and authorial artistic records. Empathy and cooperation are experienced right from respectful listening to the shared narratives, as well as in the construction of the week's study agenda together with the students, providing time for a welcome, a review of what was worked on in the previous meeting,

the development of the day's proposal and

individual and/or collective self-assessment. These proposals are pertinent and attentive to the intention of welcoming, dialogue, systematization of content and health care protocols. Strategies to anticipate the routine can have a mitigating effect on the reactions of students who are suffering from anxiety, their anxieties and insecurities, as well as keeping the channel for dialog open. Proposing a regular routine for certain activities is another possible support for students' internal organization, enabling them to activate their repertoire in advance through the opportunity to research. This form of anticipation also has the potential to reduce anxiety in the class, as it helps personalize the teaching and learning process.

Having the script of the lesson proposal in sight, with objectives, procedures and evaluation criteria known to the whole class, as the dynamics of the lesson are experienced, favors the management of events, since everyone involved in the process is sharing responsibility and is repeatedly led to reflect on their contributions and commitment.

Managing daily life in order to lead to a successful school career, imbuing practices with intentionality, requires the use of strategies that cannot be random or haphazard, given that they reflect a concept of teaching and learning, and the action dynamics of today's young people require an environment where the subject is active, participative and takes responsibility for their journey of building knowledge. Another factor to be considered is the development of proposals that either prioritize working with screens or encourage disconnection from them.

The challenge of remote learning, if on the one hand it has led to a huge portion of society daring to appropriate knowledge from digital technologies, on the other it has deepened the inequalities in access to these same technologies. By the way, looking at the issue of social gulfs and their variables - so cruel as to generate data proving that the coronavirus kills more black and poor people in Brazil and around the world (GRAGNANI, 2020) - could be pertinent content for developing appropriate strategies for exercising critical, systemic and problem-solving thinking.

While it seems unlikely that we will ever return to classes that passively tolerate lessons reduced to blackboards and chalk, the knowledge gained by teachers during this distressing time of precarious remote teaching can be improved through the collaboration of the students themselves. As well as being a promising opportunity to expand knowledge, the inversion in the dynamics of who teaches and who learns nurtures bonds and empathy, reconnecting human contact.

In this context, in the material published with the conclusions of work advised by Telma Weisz (SÃO PAULO, 2018), the profile of investigative teachers is characterized by being based on previous questions and concerns that are fundamental to educational action:

- which objectives are relevant;
- what the class's repertoire of knowledge is;
- what content will be covered;
- when and for how long the activities will take place;
- and what and how to proceed to guarantee learning.

It is in planning that the needs, potential and aspirations of the group of students serve as parameters for adapting the learning objectives and selecting the content needed to achieve them. To this end, planning the work to be carried out in the classroom starts with diagnostic surveys of the students to find out what their previous knowledge is, their potential and what they still need to learn. Once we have identified the class's repertoire of knowledge and listed the objectives to be achieved, we can proceed to systematize the content that should guarantee meaningful learning. In addition, continually making use of the resources that are feasible in terms of the time and space available and rounding off the day's agenda with a moment to appreciate the activities and one's own performance are procedures that make it possible to record information and contribute to the selection of more powerful strategies.

In addition, Weisz (2009) already emphasized the need for teachers to consider the details: • matching the theme to the interests of the class whenever possible;

- how much time will be allocated to learning possibilities at different times in relation to the complexity of the content;
- the contextualization of the lesson with social language practices, based on the relevance and achievement of the selected objectives and content;

- planning in such a way as to allow for the progressive development of the level of autonomy and determination of the class and of each student in particular;

- a curriculum arranged in a spiral, in which the contents are offered in due time, taking into account the potential of the students and the degree of depth differentiated at each sequence of activities, stage or year of the cycle;

- the learning that is possible, within the evaluation criteria, which must refer to the learning that is essential for the continuity of the process;

- promoting organized teaching from the complex to the simple and back to the complex, challenging but not unattainable;

- more explicit systematization of the essential aspects of the content worked on;

- the need for coordination between curricular components and content, with a view to interdisciplinary work whenever possible;

- reviewing activities using strategies, environments (online and face-to-face) and time slots that are relevant to the students' learning process. As for the arrangement of activities, Lerner (2002) describes three organizational modalities, which should be provided in a systematic, routine, intentional and learning-promoting way:

- project work: a sequence of activities culminating in the production of a final product

to be exhibited;

- sequences of activities: tasks to be carried out successively with the intention of leading to the acquisition of specific knowledge and, consequently, to the achievement of the learning objectives set;

- independent activities: isolated activities that can be habitual or occasional.

The criteria that really differentiate them are the frequency and duration involved in the classroom and the potential of each organizational modality for specific content.

As the different organizational modalities can be combined in the development of a single piece of work, once the objectives have been listed, they can be broken down into simpler specific objectives and brought together in such a way that the successive activities proposed to consolidate them give rise to sequences of activities. Breaking down broader objectives into more specific ones is an effective principle for designing sequences of activities that lead to the achievement of that first, broader objective.

Interpreting the achievement of each objective as a succession of phases to be conquered can provide positive feedback on the process that learners are going through to build their knowledge.

Completely adaptable to the use of various digital technologies, the methodological movements of work - collective work, in groups, in pairs and autonomously - together with the organizational modalities favor a more powerful approach to the content and guarantee a more significant quality of learning.

There are methodological movements (SÃO PAULO, 2019b) that enhance the acquisition of certain contents to the detriment of others and the spaces and times to be used need to be prepared in advance. The diversity of groupings not only contributes to learning to work collaboratively, but also helps to acquire the progressive ability to carry out activities independently.

It is possible to associate this work dynamic with the learning styles of the students (MELARÉ; BARROS, 2008), and it is of great value to provide experiences that reconcile methodological work movements and ways of learning according to the personal skills and abilities of each group of students. Approaching the same content in different ways and providing successive approaches to the same content - in a gradually deepening treatment - guarantees the expansion of learning expectations throughout the process.

In the institutional document City Curriculum: Early Childhood Education (2019a), welcoming is defined as both a principle and a working method. If it is experienced permanently in everyday life from the moment we return to face-to-face classes, it will give credibility to the intentional construction of educational work.

Although the seriousness of the situation requires constant rigor in relation to the restrictions imposed by covid-19, students cannot be deprived of an environment that inspires a sense of security and welcome, especially through classroom dynamics permeated by respect, dialogue, listening, cooperation and empathy. The process of rebuilding bonds with the school will certainly take place through opportunities to talk about feelings, past difficulties, traumatic or positive experiences, periods of isolation, meetings in the family environment and returning (CNE, 2020). Good pedagogical practices can be the result of another look at the lessons learned during the period of social distancing, combining attention to the effervescence of contemporaneity with careful systematization of activities, with a view to intentionality. A unique aspect of this tragic event is that it affected all societies in some way, although undeniably to varying degrees. This results in the broad resonance of feelings, impressions and identification not only among the students, but also between them and the teachers, since everyone was immersed in the same historical time of uncertainty and anguish (ALFAGEME, 2020).

Thus, it is up to the teacher to develop appropriate systematization that presupposes a repertoire of content that dialogues with some aspect of the

students' reality, so that, by building connections, they can extrapolate their understanding. Undoubtedly, their experiences, knowledge, potential and difficulties are a rich repertoire of possibilities for approaching curricular content organized according to the objectives to be achieved (SÃO PAULO, 2019c).

As well as analyzing the teaching reports and talking to the teacher and CP, my role as PAP also consisted of sitting next to the children and teenagers to talk about what their difficulties were and how I could help them. They taught me much more through enriching exchanges of experiences and coping strategies, in other words, reciprocal listening and reflection on difficulties and anxieties as strategies for building a repertoire of how to learn how to learn.

Repeated academic training, although relevant, often distances itself from the reality of the classroom floor and promotes reflections that have little impact on practice. As a teacher, I opted for those that provoked me to deconstruct the practices rooted in my daily actions, most of which came from my own student memories.

Although people have beautiful memories of their school days, I am one of those who have discouraging memories of the dynamics of carrying out intramural tasks and, therefore, reframing my career from the point of view of continuing education was the most appropriate starting point. Having been an elementary school student in suburban public schools in the last century, being a black woman and also a teacher in a suburban public school invites me to reflect and intervene, based on the training meetings, committed to education as a right denied to the enslaved black population for centuries, to collaborative collective work between all the social agents in the school community and to the principle of equity, essential aspects for raising the learning expectations of students from working class backgrounds.

Telma Weisz (2009) does not propose condemning the past, but recognizing that responses to contemporary demands are intertwined with this current historical moment - with its conflicting

legacies, technologies, diversities, contradictions and inequalities. This alignment is possible given teacher training that favors a better understanding of educational theories, avoiding dissonance in their adaptation to practice (SÃO PAULO, 2019c). Training in group sessions between teachers to study and identify common and recurring difficulties expands the repertoire of searching for and developing assertive practices in partnership. In order for me to make the most of these moments, it became essential for me to adopt an investigative stance on the difficulties and potential of the students and my own and, at the same time, to take notes on the teaching and learning process to be reflected on in pedagogical meetings, whether with my peers or pedagogical coordination.

Although remote teaching, which was suddenly instituted, has caused distress and discomfort by requiring education professionals to master technologies that until recently were completely unknown to many of us, access to videoconferencing, distance learning courses, digital education platforms, social networks and the Internet of Things (IOT) has provided indispensable knowledge for the environment to be built in face-to-face classes and for recording the course (SALAS, 2020), making this valuable material to be shared in teaching groups to build and improve practices that mobilize knowledge and promote learning.

We are left with a vast world of anxiety, fear and stress. There is no situation in recent human history in which everyone has been threatened at the same time. The impacts of the crisis on the daily life of societies may vary in degree and tone, but in no way can they be underestimated (PASCUAL, 2020).

Managing pain, loss, lack, frustration, impotence, boredom, surprises and joy will need to be done and requires certain learning processes. The school environment (remote and face-to-face) can be a safe, welcoming and powerful space for developing responsibility, participation, empathy and collaboration, skills needed to deal with feelings and expectations of oneself and others, develop viable, inclusive and equitable strategies and reflect on the norms and values that interfere

with people's choices and actions.

Giving due importance to planning involves selecting situations that, when problematized, add meaning that translates into life. The construction of learning by the students themselves, through the exercise of their protagonism, autonomy and determination, takes place in the dialog between teacher and student, where the latter also has an active voice in a multi-way learning process with competent mediation.

In a face-to-face environment, special attention must be paid to looking people in the eye and verbalizing what facial communication will not articulate effectively, if the use of a mask is still necessary. In some dimension the silent also suffer, so it is essential to create specific opportunities to welcome those who still resist getting involved in the proposed activities.

Using the social experiences of the group of students as clues for selecting approaches, content and strategies makes it possible to add meaning to them. Welcoming the vision of the local community into the classroom as a safe starting point enables teaching that is less content-oriented and more focused on comprehensive education (WEISZ, 2009), as well as the use of resources that enable authorial and collaborative production. Drawing up agreements with the class as to what is prudent to delimit is a useful strategy in both remote and face-to-face environments.

By looking and listening to the class, the teacher invests in the quality of the socio-affective environment and, instead of expecting students to behave in a way that is consistent with the prison model (passive between bars) or the factory model (obedient to the sirens), they develop students who are protagonists and co-responsible for their learning.

In this space and time of constructing knowledge that is different from that traditionally considered most relevant, understanding constructive error (WEISZ, 2009) also significantly interferes in the socio-affective environment, since it signals the student's reasoning in relation to that particular activity. Paying special attention to the path

and procedures the student used to reach that conclusion adds importance to the effort they put in and the knowledge they have already shown they have acquired by mobilizing it is recognized and praised.

With a view to fruitful interventions, valuable information is detected when welcoming is used as a method (WEISZ, 2009). Dedication to playing the role of reflective teacher suggests mediation in essence and the permanent search for an understanding of how the student thinks and arrives at a particular line of reasoning. This only becomes feasible thanks to the teacher's training repertoire, which enables them to map the students' knowledge-building trajectory and intervene (via replanning) to enhance the possibilities of overcoming the class's difficulties and expanding their knowledge.

This interdependence between all the people involved in the process at the same historical moment helps to establish productive links and collaborative relationships. The proper organization and distribution of activities enhances the autonomy and co-responsibility of the class in the dynamics of the lesson, just as the evaluation of the process, with clear criteria, and the practice of self-assessment, through frequent activities, intensify this co-responsibility.

Planning involves checking the students' conditions and this action presupposes periodically revisiting the notes documented during the process.

The organizational modalities and the methodological movement of work are powerful allies when harmonized with the nature of the content, learning needs and the use of technological tools according to the objectives and specificity of the content (LERNER, 2002). In other words, the study and analysis of the objectives shows which necessary knowledge must be mobilized in order to design viable activities that make the objectives attainable.

It is suggested that the learning and self-assessment roadmaps be built with the class, listing goals, activity proposals and assessment criteria that

will help to make teaching as personalized and stimulating as possible. They are flexible and carefully designed.

Checking the students' conditions, the repertoire from which they will build other associations and being clear about which way of working enhances learning; these are criteria that need to be shared with the class as a strategy for developing guided reflection, shared responsibility, determination and autonomy in each student (SÃO PAULO, 2019a). Aware that hearing praise can be just as uncomfortable as receiving criticism, ethical teachers cannot shy away from having their performance evaluated reciprocally.

CONCLUSION

In view of the history of exclusion suffered by the working classes - especially women and the black population - the active and obstinate search for all students must be promoted, since the school dropout rate - a ghost always lurking in the reports of the most vulnerable communities - is the educational challenge to be overcome in the post-pandemic world and acting on reality implies developing strategies to deal with contradictions and conflicts, improving means of social participation (Chauí, 2008).

When planning educational activities, it is essential to pay attention to the development of each particular lesson in its details, including and essentially in compliance with health protection protocols, whose routine serves as an instrument that helps organize and distribute teaching actions in time and space for successful learning and health safety for all (CNE, 2020).

Although widely flexible in many aspects, the organization to maximize and coordinate the use of didactic time is a decisive item in the process, since it involves working with activities (SALAS, 2020) to build the knowledge of each individual student, as well as the time needed to take care of the health protocols, welcoming, listening, intervening, evaluating and overcoming difficulties.

In conclusion, by integrating moments of reflection

on the assessment of learning with students into planning, we give them the opportunity to discuss, in a respectful and reflective way, the difficulties, strategies and resources we use to develop skills and build knowledge. In addition, it is the ethical duty of everyone involved in welcoming actions to respect each person's learning processes, experiences of loss and protection protocols so that the educational environment promotes health for all dimensions of the person (CNE, 2020).

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COGNITIVE DEVELOPMENT OF AUTIST STUDENTS: A CASE STUDY ABOUT THE SUPPORT TEACHER AT COLÉGIO ESTADUAL DE GOIATUBA (GO)

AUTHORS

Elismárcia Luiz Moura Santos: Graduated in Pedagogy and Letters from UniCerrado - Centro Universitário de Goiatuba, Specialist in Educational Guidance from Universidade Salgado de Oliveira and Clinical Neuropsychopedagogy from FATEC - Faculdade de Tecnologia do Vale do Ivaí and Master in Educational Sciences from Universidade del Sol - Unades/PY.

ABSTRACT

Autism is among the Autistic Spectrum Disorders (ASD) most present in people, it is usually detected in childhood and, mainly, when the child starts his school life. Autistic disorders are complex neurological disorders that affect the acquisition of diverse skills throughout life. To be able to help students reach their full potential, it is necessary to understand this disorder and its characteristics, as well as the essential elements for this student to achieve school success. This article aimed to analyze whether students with Autistic Spectrum Disorder can develop their cognitive skills in the school context and the importance of the Support teacher in this process. The methodology used was a qualitative approach and case study, the instruments used were the observation report and a semi-structured interview with the Support teacher and with the teachers of the Portuguese Language and Mathematics subjects. The study concluded that understanding the feelings of the autistic is essential for success in learning to happen, however, the teachers of the curricular subjects do not have training aimed at teaching this group and, much less, availability in the classroom to do so, as generally the rooms are overcrowded, and it becomes impossible to get the individualized attention they need. In this way, the Support teacher is the key piece for learning to take place. Future studies should be more comprehensive and address all students diagnosed with autism in state, municipal, and private schools to understand the importance and essentiality of the Support teacher, since, sometimes, the school system itself has the belief that the regent teacher could teach this student, thus making the presence of the Support teacher unnecessary.

Keywords: Autistic Spectrum Disorder. Autism. Support Teacher. Cognitive. Development.

INTRODUCTION

The term autism, derived from the German autism and the Greek autus meaning “self”, was first introduced by the Swiss psychiatrist Eugen Bleuler in 1911 to describe schizophrenic symptomatology in adult patients (social withdrawal with interior withdrawal). From 1943, Leo Kanner used this term to differentiate it from schizophrenia, then the subject of numerous American studies that sought to base child psychiatry on the Bleulerian entity.

Kanner’s study was, of course, groundbreaking, but it is also important to note that even earlier descriptions of children who probably had autism were done in the 1800s at a training school for the intellectually disabled and in the 1700s with some reports of wild children.

Michael Rutter, a leading child psychiatric researcher at Maudsley Hospital in the United Kingdom who conducted the first genetic study of autism, stated in 1972 that “the autistic child has a fantasy deficiency rather than an excess” (RUTTER, 1983, p. 514).). The meaning of the word autism was then radically reformulated from describing someone who fantasized excessively to someone who did not fantasize at all.

The researcher followed an autistic student in the 6th grade of Elementary School in the final year at the school, which works as a high school teacher. At the time, the researcher presented Elisio Joaquim de Vasconcelos, in Goiatuba, to the management group of the State College of the Military Police of the State of Goiás – Elisio Joaquim de Vasconcelos, her research project and what motivated the choice of such a theme. On that occasion, the principal, the coordinator and the Support teacher, as well as the Portuguese Language and Mathematics teachers, authorized both the research and the monitoring of the student during the classes of the aforementioned disciplines.

METHODOLOGICAL FRAMEWORK

The observational study was carried out with an autistic student studying in the 6th of Elementary School at the State College of the Military Police of the State of Goiás – Elisio Joaquim de Vasconcelos, in Goiatuba, Goiás. This school unit was chosen because it is the field of work of the researcher,

which facilitated the design of the research. It was instituted by Law nº 18.967 of 07/22/2015, located at Rua São Paulo nº 816, Centro, in the city of Goiatuba – Goiás.

This research is descriptive of the observational type. Observational studies allow for adapting to the specific needs of each investigation. However, in general terms, an observational study of the longitudinal category.

For the elaboration of this study, bibliographical research was carried out in Portuguese, English and Spanish with the keywords: autism, learning, and teacher of Support, since this review made it possible to summarize the research already completed and to obtain conclusions from the proposed theme. In addition to the bibliographic research, observation reports and interviews were used with the Support teacher, Luciana, and the Portuguese Language and Mathematics teachers.

The report refers to a statement, written or oral, that describes the qualities, characteristics and context of some event. It is, therefore, an orderly elaboration based on observation and analysis. The purpose of preparing a report is highly variable, although it always presupposes the eventual need to inform others about something that happened (BRÁNEZ, 2013).

RESULTS ANALYSIS AND DISCUSSION

The research was carried out with 1 (one) student diagnosed with autism. Thus, a non-participant observation was carried out in which the researcher accompanied the student and the teacher from August to December 2019. The data were presented in the form of observation reports. The author spoke with the Mathematics and Portuguese teachers, the most critical subjects for Márcio, and with the Support teacher who accompanies the student.

During my observations I paid close attention to communication and language problems, I know that there is a strong sensory component involved in the difficulty of people with autism in developing a two-way and functional model of communication. These factors related to sensory disorders have a strong impact on language acquisition, intellectual development, behaviour and social interaction. There is profuse scientific literature on the subject, both at the auditory and motor level, as well as in

the processing of this information.

With the research carried out, it can be said that autism is still under study since there are many differences between theorists in the field of science. The information found here may shed some light on what the world of a child with autism is like.

Another point analyzed is in line with what was stated as a hypothesis: "It is considered that the limitations of the autistic student may not be of a cognitive nature, that is, he can develop more one area of knowledge than another, therefore, the teacher does not must limit it must, yes, try it in all areas of knowledge: languages and technologies, exact and human".

"The Support teacher plays a fundamental role in the development of the autistic student, as he is dealing directly with this student and with his emotions and limitations".

One of the authors (BARBERINI, 2016) confirms the hypothesis when he said that autistic children can develop different abilities than children with normal development. They may also develop skills in a different order than other children. Regarding the role of the Support teacher, it is to guarantee the presence, participation and evolution of students with disabilities in the classroom, without exception. Maturana and Mendes (2015), citing research carried out by Takala et al. (2009) in Finland, defined three different situations based on three alternative support approaches:

The first approach: individualized teaching - Was found to be effective in providing individual attention, but raised concerns for three different reasons: the pressure that could be put on supported students, the lack of contact between these students and the rest of the class, and the stigma of being separated from the common context.

The second approach: teaching in small groups - Was considered favourable due to the possibility of offering support in a peaceful environment, but also raised concerns about how some students

suffered when they were removed from their peers. They felt stigmatized and missed out on what was worked on in the regular classroom. Teaching in small groups did not offer the possibility of sufficient individual attention. To avoid this stigma and minimize the difference. In research carried out in the classroom to include children with autism, Lindsay et al. (2014) observed the benefits of having a mix of different children with the Support teacher to do some tasks. The criterion was never the level of the children: any child could receive additional help.

Goffman (1982) emphasized that prejudices structure what one person imagines of the other, which in the face of someone with a stigma defines him or her as partially human. According to the author, one way to camouflage the perception of the stigmatized person is to use subterfuges by pointing out other differences. Thus, a stigma theory is constructed, an ideology to explain their inferiority and without realizing the danger it represents, sometimes rationalizing the animosity based on other differences, such as social class.

The stigma attributed to people with disabilities and ASD is not only about what is visible in their physical characteristics but mainly with the aforementioned condition, associated with another, resulting in the stigma of inferiority, disability and discrimination. These are constructed under a socially elaborated standard of judgment based on normative expectations. The third approach: collaborative teaching with two teachers - It was the modality with the best results and most preferred by teachers. In this approach, more children could have access to support and this allowed them to remain in the classroom without losing any content (MATURANA; MENDES, 2015).

From an inclusive perspective, the Support teacher changes roles from focusing on individual rehabilitation-oriented attention to sharing class time and responsibilities with all students in the group along with the class teacher, and to sharing class time classes and activities between two teachers and improving the overall response to student diversity.

Huguet (2009) emphasizes that it is necessary to agree all together about activities, groupings, spatial distribution and so on. Second, teachers need to agree on the type of participation each will have in activities and their involvement in student assessment. Third, while the scope of activities can be broad enough to address diversity, consideration should be given to the participation of children with more learning difficulties and ensure that they receive the attention they need from their primary teacher or teacher. of support. Finally, the entire experience must be evaluated to plan possible changes and improvements.

Thus, to talk about the autistic child in the school context, it was necessary to quote Wallon, Piaget and Vygotsky, as the authors talk about the development of the human being in general, and every child needs stimuli from the environment to develop. and school is a very stimulating environment, and this stimulus is even more important for children with Autistic Spectrum Disorder. As for the family, another author, Lima (2019), referred to this group as the initial stimulus group for children with autism and that the functions of people with autism are: to care for and ensure their survival, educate them and train them to live in the social community to which they belong.

About the perception of the student I followed, I realized that he learns effectively when the support teacher uses concrete materials, and the main challenge for him is dealing with emotions. Another factor is the routine, the autistic student has to have a systematic routine because anything that escapes from it, the student changes his mood and when he is in an altered mood, he does not learn and does not fix what is being exposed to him.

CONCLUSION

Working on the theme “Autism in the school context: the relevance of the Support teacher”, represented a personal challenge from the perspective of the authors addressed here and the researcher’s vision about the challenges of Special Education. And in response to the hypotheses raised, the researcher can state that the autistic student can develop cognitive skills independent of the disorder and that the presence of a Support

teacher is essential for the school insertion process to be effective.

The authors made important contributions regarding legislation that, in a way, protects students with various disabilities, including students with Autistic Spectrum Disorder. In addition to the laws, another point observed was the presence of the family in the life of the autistic, even though several authors defend the importance of the family in the social insertion of the autistic, I believe that the lack of socialization does not depend on the family environment, it is usually of neurological origin, rather than contrary to other people with disabilities who intervene in family dynamics and the socialization process.

Thus, the importance of the Support teacher is notorious and fundamental. If each student learns differently, the autistic needs even more individualized attention, not only to teach but to listen. Understanding his feelings and often really being the one who supports him, who values his achievements and who is close to when he feels insecure or afraid.

In this way, it is considered that with increasingly crowded classrooms and with more autistic students, debating the importance of this professional is very relevant since he is fundamental for the development of the autistic, and one of the greatest difficulties of autism begins in verbal development. and language. Having a professional able to listen, understand, support and individualize the teaching process with a specific focus on the student and their individual needs, cognitive development becomes concrete. The fundamental thing is that, in addition to the potential of each autistic, it is that in their environment they find support, encouragement and the necessary ways to build their integrity, with new learning that will provide them with the necessary tools for personal development, which is inclusive in the context in which it operates.

It is possible to integrate and include autistic people both in school and social spaces, as well as in family spaces, their progress will depend on how the teacher will work with them, not limiting how much they learned, but the quality of what was learned, that is, showing within of his activities, his posture at home and school, such

as how to fit his school supplies in his backpack, collect and store the materials or toys he has used, or help with household chores, such as organizing the room he occupies, help the mother to set the table, among other tasks.

On the one hand, the articulation of actions within the Inclusive Special Education modality must be strengthened to facilitate the support that students with autism require to achieve the curricular objectives proposed by the school, facilitating an effective social integration and, on the other hand, the integration these students through actions articulated with the levels and other modalities of the National Education System.

The study showed that the targeted and individualized support of an education professional is essential for students with autism to develop their academic skills. If each student learns differently, the autistic needs even more individualized attention, not only to learn curricular and academic activities but also to learn to listen and understand command voices.

The study concluded that understanding the feelings of the autistic is essential for success in learning to happen, however, the teachers of the curricular subjects do not have training aimed at teaching this group and, much less, availability in the classroom to do so, as generally the rooms are overcrowded and it becomes impossible to get the individualized attention they need. In this way, the Support teacher is the key piece for learning to take place.

Future studies should be more comprehensive and address all students diagnosed with autism in state, municipal and private schools to understand the importance and essentiality of the Support teacher, since, sometimes, the school system itself has the belief that the regent teacher can teach this student, thus making the presence of the Support teacher unnecessary.

RECOMMENDATIONS

- Carry out courses, workshops and seminars for understanding between Asperger's and autism.
- Carry out workshops or training courses in special education and preparation of curricular

and pedagogical adaptations, etc. In and for effective inclusive education, at least once a year, at the beginning of each administration.

- Each classroom should not only have a class teacher, but also a permanent assistant who can help students diagnosed with autism.

- Each student diagnosed with autism must have a Support teacher in the classroom so that they have a more personalized learning process so that the results are optimal and are reflected in their school performance.

- Teachers, in particular, should seek information in the different means of communication so that they have more knowledge about the needs, forms and rhythms of learning that students with a diagnosis of autism have.

- Teachers, without exception, must make curricular and didactic adaptations, from planning to development in the classroom, lesson by lesson.

- Hold courses, workshops or seminars for teachers and parents so that they have more knowledge on how to help in the process of adaptation, not only educationally, but also socially and culturally, of children diagnosed with autism.

- Another very important recommendation is that the Ministry of Education establish fixed qualitative parameters to describe and classify the school performance of these children diagnosed with autism on a scale, such as: good, very good, medium, and bad, from the interview with the teachers and the director, there is no qualitative parameter regulated by the ministry.

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CONTENT ANALYSIS OF THE SOCIAL REPRESENTATION IN THE NARRATIVES OF CHRONIC PATIENTS

AUTHORS

Camila Cristina Rodrigues: Nurse. Master in Semiotics, Information Technology and Education. doctoral student in Public Health – UNIVERSIDAD UNIDA - Paraguay.

Ricardo De Bonis: PhD, teacher of the discipline Ethics in Academic Production (Universidad UNIDA) CEO – iiEP Institute.

ABSTRACT

In an interdisciplinary approach, we found a possible reading in the analyzed article: “Construction of Meaning in the Narratives of Chronic Patients” and the construction of an analysis based on the expressed content. This construction of speech permeates the entire process of human communication being developed through the relationship of linguistic symbols expressed in speech, that is, in the speech emanated by the subject. Objective: To analyze the content of textual fragments of the article “Construction of meaning in the narratives of chronically ill patients” by José Roque Junges and Tatiane Bagatini under the framework of Moscovici’s social representation. Methodology: Research with a qualitative approach. For treatment of the material, Bardin’s method of content analysis (1977) was chosen, where he analyzes the content and its inferences in a systematic and objective way, described by Minayo (2000), which organizes it in three stages: analysis, exploration of the material and treatment of the results obtained and interpretation under the framework of Moscovici (1979; 2003; 2009). Results and Discussion: In this study, we used the inferences to compose the content analysis categories, associating them by similarity, generating the categories: diagnosis of the disease, therapeutic and drug treatment become (1) Therapeutic, while body and emotional situation become (2) Social Representation. We emphasize that all respondents are in a moment of physical, emotional, and social fragility resulting from the hospitalization process, which limits full autonomy over health decisions and practices. Final Considerations: We found in the analyzes of the study two distinct processes in the discourse confirming our hypothesis about the attitude influenced by everyday experiences, the study presents objectification and anchoring analyzed based on TRS that demonstrate the role of influence of the daily experience and the transformation of the subjective into objective through the hierarchy of responsibility for their reality.

Keywords: Content Analysis, Discourse, Chronic Patient , Social Representation.

INTRODUCTION

Chronic noncommunicable diseases (NCDs) according to the World Health Organization are classified in a list that includes cardiovascular and cerebrovascular diseases, diabetes mellitus, obstructive respiratory diseases, asthma and neoplasms. In this same list we currently find mental disorders, neurological, oral, bone, joint, auditory diseases, osteoporosis and genetic disorders. (WHO, 2005; THEME FILHA, 2015)

According to Simões et al (2021), the National Health Surveys (INS) allow knowing the profile, distribution and risk factors that affect a given population by analyzing the geographic variables that prevail in each group of diseases. The study evaluated NCDs such as neuropsychiatric disorders (NP), musculoskeletal disorders (MSDs) and joint disorders, in addition to chronic renal failure (CRF).

A striking characteristic of CNCDs is the longevity of symptoms, fatigue caused by hospitalizations, long treatments, disabilities, social restrictions generating biological, psychological and social consequences that can be identified in social representations and discourses. (SILVA; CREPALDI; BOUSFIELD, 2021)

Due to the need for qualified listening for these developments, the Ministry of Health (MS) created a public policy called the National Humanization Policy – Humaniza SUS in 2003, among the strategies included qualified listening. This qualified listening, in addition to understanding the processes that the patient experiences, determines possible therapeutic itineraries. (BRASIL 2004; SANTOS, 2019)

In an interdisciplinary approach, we found a possible reading in the analyzed article: “Construction of Meaning in the Narratives of Chronic Patients” and the construction of an analysis based on the expressed content. This construction of speech permeates the entire process of human communication being developed through the relationship of linguistic symbols expressed in speech, that is, in the speech emanated by the subject.

Through this, the question emerges: What is the

social representation that we find in the discourse of chronically ill patients according to Moscovici’s theory of social relations?

Our hypothesis is based on the fact that the construction of the discourse undergoes modification due to the result of socio-economic relations and the construction of the meaning of the disease. The social representation expressed in the speeches will be supported by the attitudes and social influence experienced.

We believe that the prevailing social representation in the discourse is supported by influence relationships and social perception regarding their current health situation and intrapsychic conflicts. generated. The relevance of this study is supported by the belief that the speech undergoes different modifications when interpreted from the perspective of social relations.

GOAL

To analyze the content of fragments of the article “Construction of meaning in the narratives of chronically ill patients” by José Roque Junges and Tatiane Bagatini under the framework of Moscovici’s social representation.

METHODOLOGY

Research with a qualitative approach to the book “ Construction of meaning in the narratives of chronically ill patients” by José Roque Junges and Tatiane Bagatini published in the Revista da Associação Médica Brasileira in 2010. For the treatment of the material, Bardin’s method of content analysis (1977) was chosen.) where it analyzes the content and its inferences in a systematic and objective way described by Minayo (2000) who organizes the material in three stages: analysis, exploration of the material and treatment of the obtained results and interpretation. In this study, the framework of Moscovici (1979; 2003; 2009) called Theory of Social Representations (TSR) will be applied.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The article under analysis contextualizes the

technologies used in the Unified Health System, referencing the democratizing role of access to treatments, argues that technology can cause a distancing effect on quality issues between the professional and the system user.

He states that based on this fact, the Ministry of Health created the Humaniza SUS Program in order to elaborate a specific policy, but we find refutation of this idea in the study by Rios (2009, p.255) who refers to the formulation based on the historical and social context and not merely in terms of user visibility in the system.

Humanization recognizes the field of subjectivities as a fundamental instance for a better understanding of problems and for the search for shared solutions. Participation, autonomy, responsibility and solidarity are values that characterize this way of doing health that results, in the end, in more quality care and better working conditions. Its essence is the alliance of technical and technological competence with ethical and relational competence .

The griffin above affirms the importance of subjectivity, but combined with technical and technological competence. We find in technical competence the issue of qualified listening, that is, attentive listening with the purpose of welcoming the user and bonding. (COELHO; JORGE, 2009) The study authors describe the use of a qualitative approach through a semi-structured questionnaire, the study sample 17 participants between 25 and 65 years old hospitalized in a public hospital unit in the metropolitan region of Porto Alegre. The study does not describe within the initial sample how many respondents are in these characteristics, it states the use of only 6 interviews for analysis. It is important to emphasize that the study was evaluated by the Ethics Committee of UNISINOS with Resolution nº 053/2004.

The sample of the material analyzed is predominantly female, which demonstrates a fragility in the analyzes as it makes it impossible to verify the existence of a pattern of discourse between groups and genders.

In the results and discussion, we found the organization of the speech in the utterance, being composed of categories such as: diagnosis of the disease, therapeutic treatment, body, medicine, emotional situation, being analyzed in the light of the Bakhtinian Theory.

In this study, we will use the identified inferences to compose categories for content analysis through similarity: “disease diagnosis, therapeutic and drug treatment” become (1) Therapeutics, while “body and emotional situation” become (2) Social Representation.

Below is an expository table with the categories and textual fragments for analysis according to Moscovici’s theory of social representation.

CHART 1: ORGANIZATION OF CATEGORIES AND TEXTUAL FRAGMENTS. MOGI DAS CRUZES, 2023.

Therapy	<p>“Ah, sometimes I get really sad because I think I went to eat those things I couldn’t. Now it’s late. Now you have to live your life” (Textual fragment 1)</p> <p>“No, because this is something that runs in the family, because the old people had it, my mother, my father and all the brothers. Some have already died” (Textual fragment 2)</p> <p>“Ah, I think that if I do my treatment correctly, eat what the doctor says, then there will be salvation. If I do everything wrong, I will never recover” (Textual fragment 3)</p> <p>“Look, I think it’s the psychologist. We can vent, talk a lot, I cry, I talk. It’s not just giving an injection or giving a sleeping pill. I think it’s better to sit down and talk than give medicine” (Textual fragment 4)</p>
Social Representation	<p>(1) I found out because of high blood pressure (a) when I was pregnant - I left the hospital - very heavy body, I walked with that weight - always heavy belly, always stuffed (b) I went to the maternity ward - I had swollen feet and a hundred or so kilos, it was all liquid in the body. (2) “I went for an exam, an ultrasound, I had to undergo hemodialysis” - “I was all swollen, everything was liquid” - “I felt tired, heavy” (c) “When I went to deliver the child, it looked like I was going to gain more than a baby” (Textual fragment 5)</p>

Source: JUNGES, J. R.; BAGATINI, T.. Construction of meaning in the narratives of chronically ill patients. *Journal of the Brazilian Medical Association*, v. 56, n.2, p. 179-185)

We can verify in the therapeutic category in the textual fragment (1) and (3) the reference to situations related to the act or dietary restriction reflects a social issue, eating is a social and gregarious act and is subject to interference from the place where the individual is inserted.

Fragment 1: “ Ah, sometimes I get really sad because I think I went to eat those things I couldn't . Now it's late. Now you have to take life ”. (GRIFFIN OUR)

Fragment 3 : “Ah, I think that if I do my treatment correctly, eat what the doctor says , then there will be salvation. If I get it all wrong, I'll never recover.” (GRIFFIN OUR)

Applying the Theory of Social Representation, we find the statement in the studies of Samuel and Polli (2020) :

[...] social representations can be understood as the re-presentation of everyday phenomena. This re-presentation occurs when people collectively think, position themselves, express themselves and share thoughts and reproduce social representations. To get to know the world and make it more controllable and close, people create social representations. That is, the individual actively participates in the construction of social thought, explaining and giving meaning to everyday facts [...]

We found in fragments (2) and (4) the discourse of the need to recognize family situations that interfere in the current dynamics of the interviewee's life, but Mosconici (1979) starts from the belief that there is no cut between the external universe and the individual (group) and yes, of its interrelationship between the subject and the other subject. Thus, the author refers to the reciprocal influence of the social structure and that of the subject.

Fragment 2: No, because this is something that runs in the family, because the old people had it, my mother, my father and all the brothers. Some have already died

Fragment 4 : “ Look, I think it's the psychologist. We can vent, talk a lot, I cry, I talk. It's not just giving an injection or giving a sleeping pill. I think it's better to sit and talk than to give medicine”

In the Social Representation category, we can verify the discourse associated with the interviewee's discovery of the need for hemodialysis treatment:

Fragment 5: (1) I found out because of high blood pressure (a) when I was pregnant - I left the hospital - very heavy body, I walked with that weight - belly always heavy, always stuffed (b) I went to be given birth at the maternity ward - I had swollen feet and a hundred and something kilos, it was all liquid in the body. (2) “I went for an exam, an ultrasound, I had to undergo hemodialysis” - “I was all swollen, everything was liquid” - “I felt tired, heavy” (c) “When I went to deliver the child, it looked like I was going to gain more than a baby”

It is noteworthy that some speech characteristics only describe characteristics of the end of the third gestational trimester. The report describes pregnancy complications: (1) I found out because of high blood pressure (a) when I was pregnant - I left the hospital - very heavy body, I walked with that weight - belly always heavy, always stuffed (b) I went to gain weight in the maternity ward - I was with swollen feet and three hundred pounds, it was all liquid in her body.

Already in the part: (1) I found out because of high blood pressure (a) when I was pregnant, we can reflect different situations: I was having prenatal care so I was considered high risk? If so, the interlocutor could have already received the guidelines, requiring adherence to treatment.

Gomes, Mendonça and Pontes (2002, p.1210) state:

“How would this event be expressed and how would it be possible to understand it? The idea of text, as a written fixation

of discourse, allows the rehabilitation of theories of discourse in their temporal updating, contemplating the meaning of the message, which persists and must be understood.”

The article by Junges and Bagatini (2010) reports that the interviewed group presents a predominance of morbidities: diabetes mellitus (DM), systemic arterial hypertension (SAH), chronic renal failure (CRF) and depression. It is worth mentioning that all interviewees are in a moment of physical, emotional and social fragility, the hospitalization process is presented in a coercive way, that is, without full autonomy of decision about their health, these situations and speeches emanated suffer this isolation bias Social.

According to the Theory of Social Representations (SRT), we identified in the composition of the speeches the presence of intrapsychic and interpersonal conflicts, latent and “covered” attitudes towards the restrictions that the disease emanates, the presence of information about their health-disease process with preponderance the hierarchization and lack of autonomy of decisions. (SANTOS, 1994)

FINAL CONSIDERATIONS

We found in the analysis of the study two processes in the speech confirming our hypothesis about the attitude influenced by everyday experiences. The study presents objectification and anchoring described in TRS. Objectification is related to the formulation of ideas based on the categorization of feelings contained in the speeches, such as ordering and classifying actions, turning something subjective into real. The anchoring present in the speeches is observed in the discourse of the hierarchy of values and meanings resulting from the progressive process of the disease.

It is important to contextualize that in some speeches we find the statement “improvement when talking” with a psychologist, which should not be identified by the interviewee because it generates the false idea that qualified listening occurs only by this professional and not by a

multidisciplinary team.

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DEMOCRATIC MANAGEMENT AND THE SPECIFICITY OF THE SCHOOL FOR ADOLESCENTS IN COMPLIANCE WITH A SOCIO-EDUCATIONAL MEASURE

AUTHORS

Paula Rosangela Gonçalves da Costa: PhD student in Educational Sciences at Universidad UNIDA in Ciudad del Leste. Master in Educational Sciences from the Universidad Americana in Asuncion. Graduated in Letters and School Management from (UFRGS) Federal University of Rio Grande do Sul. Throughout her academic career, recently school applying the precepts of democratic management.

Benedita Augusta Ferreira Furtado: PhD student in Educational Sciences at Universidad UNIDA. Master in Educational Sciences from the Universidad Americana in Asuncion. Pedagogue specialist in Early Childhood Education and School Management.

ABSTRACT

In an interdisciplinary approach, we found a possible reading in the analyzed article: “Construction of Meaning in the Narratives of Chronic Patients” and the construction of an analysis based on the expressed content. This construction of speech permeates the entire process of human communication being developed through the relationship of linguistic symbols expressed in speech, that is, in the speech emanated by the subject. Objective: To analyze the content of textual fragments of the article “Construction of meaning in the narratives of chronically ill patients” by José Roque Junges and Tatiane Bagatini under the framework of Moscovici’s social representation. Methodology: Research with a qualitative approach. For treatment of the material, Bardin’s method of content analysis (1977) was chosen, where he analyzes the content and its inferences in a systematic and objective way, described by Minayo (2000), which organizes it in three stages: analysis, exploration of the material and treatment of the results obtained and interpretation under the framework of Moscovici (1979; 2003; 2009). Results and Discussion: In this study, we used the inferences to compose the content analysis categories, associating them by similarity, generating the categories: diagnosis of the disease, therapeutic and drug treatment become (1) Therapeutic, while body and emotional situation become (2) Social Representation. We emphasize that all respondents are in a moment of physical, emotional, and social fragility resulting from the hospitalization process, which limits full autonomy over health decisions and practices. Final Considerations: We found in the analyzes of the study two distinct processes in the discourse confirming our hypothesis about the attitude influenced by everyday experiences, the study presents objectification and anchoring analyzed based on TRS that demonstrate the role of influence of the daily experience and the transformation of the subjective into objective through the hierarchy of responsibility for their reality.

Keywords: Content Analysis, Discourse, Chronic Patient , Social Representation.

INTRODUCTION

This work is the result of my training as a student of the School Management Specialization course, of the National School of Basic Education Managers Program, promoted by the Graduate Program in Education at the Federal University of Rio Grande do Sul.

The in-depth examination of the central theoretical issues studied in that course made this work possible. Thus, in the “Theoretical Reference” section, the authors who contributed to the considerations regarding the themes of the right to education, Democratic Management and the Political-Pedagogical Project are presented.

Quality public education is a right guaranteed by the Federal Constitution of 1988. It is everyone’s right and a duty of the State and the family and must be promoted and encouraged with the collaboration of society as a whole, so that the person has full development and preparation for the exercise of citizenship and qualification for work.

The changes within the school result from democratic management. These changes always indicate a path towards development and training, allowing for improvements in both pedagogical and administrative issues. The democratic manager must present pedagogical spaces that allow students to build learning directed to the exercise of citizenship. In addition to teachers and staff, parents and guardians also participate in these pedagogical spaces. They are spaces for collective participation, rich in learning possibilities for everyone involved in them.

The process of democratic management begins with the elaboration of the school’s political-pedagogical project, which must have the participation of education professionals who work within the scope of the school institution. It is also necessary that the pedagogical project be widely discussed with the entire school community, prioritizing issues such as access, permanence and quality of public education.

In chapter 3, I address action research, defining it as a methodology that allows listening and approximation between all segments of a school community. For these reflections, I relied on

authors such as Maria Amélia Santoro Franco.

Widely used in education, action research presupposes a permanent dialogue between the researched subjects and the researcher, between theory and practice. In this way, a process is built between people in the school community to transform a pre-existing reality, which no longer satisfies, to develop improvements and qualify relationships.

I conclude the work by presenting, in the final considerations, the possibility of applying an intervention project that takes into account the different reality of the school where I work, whose main characteristic lies in the public served: adolescents in compliance with socio-educational measures.

2 THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

The challenge of this work is to establish a relationship between the right to education and democratic school management, as principles evidenced in practice during the reflection process on the re-elaboration of the Political-Pedagogical Project – PPP of a school with very specific peculiarities in its school community. In the development of the work, it was necessary to deepen theoretical questions that would allow to substantiate the proposed task.

2.1 RIGHT TO EDUCATION

The Federal Constitution of Brazil, of 1988, in its article 205, establishes that education is a right of all and a duty of the State and the family, being promoted and encouraged with the collaboration of society, so that the person has full development and preparation for the exercise of citizenship and qualification for work.

In order for this right to be achieved under the terms guaranteed by the Constitution, the Law of Guidelines and Bases for Education (Law No. State duties in relation to public school education “defining the responsibilities, in collaboration, between the Union, the States, the Federal District and the Municipalities”.

In the process of revision of the Federal Constitution,

which lasted from 1987 to 1988 (Procópio, 2007), the intention to profoundly reorganize the Brazilian political system prevailed. In practice, this did not happen because the attention of the National Congress and institutions turned to the economic priorities that Brazil adhered to at the time, especially after the implementation of the Real Plan and the election of Fernando Henrique Cardoso.

From 1980 onwards, Brazilian democracy gradually solidified in a formal and informal way. The confidence that the population now has in the consolidation of democracy is linked to the experiences acquired in overcoming crises and in improving the socioeconomic conditions of the population. Brazilian education becomes a government strategy within the process of establishing and solidifying democracy in Brazil.

Education is universally regarded as a Human Right; she considers Man in his vocation to always seek something better, to bring about development for himself and his community. Unlike other living beings, human beings always seek to overcome their condition of existence in the world. And he achieves this by making use of his work, transforming nature and living in society. According to Sacavino (2006):

By exercising these capacities, the human being makes history, transforms the world, being present in it in a permanent and active way. And education is a fundamental element for realizing this human vocation, understanding education in its different meanings, in the formal scope of the school system and in the non-formal scope. (SACAVINO, 2006, p.458).

Despite all the national legislation that protects the right to education, the number of Brazilians without access to school and quality education is still significant. Of those who enter school, a large portion cannot remain to complete their schooling, as stated by Sacavino (2006, p.463-464) “Of 100 students who enter elementary school, only 59 manage to finish eighth grade and only 40 reach at the end of high school”.

Of the large portion that drop out of school,

especially in elementary school, many find crime along the way and become part of the group of adolescents who are deprived of their freedom while complying with socio-educational measures.

Given this, we see that the right to education is much broader than the right to school. Educational processes permeate people's entire lives in different dimensions and phases, enabling decision-making that interferes positively or negatively in individuals' lives.

2.2 DEMOCRATIC MANAGEMENT

The function of the democratic manager in education is of fundamental importance to establish the construction of democracy in the country and, as Procópio (2007, p.15) points out, it must be in tune with the “[...] democratization of the demands of the various segments that make up the educational process and the construction of a new shared knowledge .”

The society that demands quality public education from the State is the same that defends a school committed to the community in which it operates, and whose management must be shared by the school community. The defense of democratic school management is based on the premise that all those interested and involved in school life must participate in decisions that affect school life.

In the path of democratic management, vigorous complementary and ordinary legislation has been instituted to build an organizational structure that allows the realization of the objectives and principles of national education. Today, the educational manager can make use of the Statute of the Child and Adolescent – Law nº 8.069, of 1990 – to guarantee access to education and permanence in school, in addition to the Law of Guidelines and Bases of National Education – Law nº 9.394, of 1996 – and the National Education Plan – Law No. 10,172, of 2001.

According to Medeiros and Luce (2012, p.10), this entire legal framework brings with it measures

of greater participation and social inclusion and serves as a journey “for the democratization of education and the democratization of educational management”.

Democratic management presupposes the idea of participation, of shared work, guided by a collective will and acting on the process of building a competent school committed to society. Like this,

The creation of participatory environments is, therefore, a basic condition of democratic management. One of them is the creation of an overall view of the school and its social responsibility; the establishment of internal and external associations; valuing and maximizing the multiple and diversified aptitudes and competences of the participants; the development of an open, ethical and transparent communication process. This participatory environment gives people the opportunity to control their own work, at the same time that they feel like an organic part of a reality and not just an appendage to it or a mere instrument for achieving its institutional objectives. (LÜCK, 2000, p.27).

A school with quality teaching attracts students instead of repelling them. It is also the function of the director of the school institution, within a democratic management, to present an attractive school to the community. The longer children and adolescents remain at school, the lower the chances of being swept away by crime and its consequent violence.

It is in the process of democratic management that changes occur in schools. The democratic manager presents pedagogical spaces that allow students to build learning aimed at exercising citizenship. The school can be a pedagogical space for collective participation, rich in learning possibilities for the exercise of citizenship.

In the current educational context, the theme “Democratic and Participative School Management” acquires great relevance both for its strategic nature and for its use as a tool for obtaining quality education. Where everyone can contribute to building a school that meets the

demands of the globalized world in its multiple perspectives, that is, in the formation of critical and qualified citizens to meet the demands of the job market. (CABRAL, 2011, p.2).

The perspective of democratic management, according to Cabral (2011, p.2) requires the manager to assume the commitment to re-educate himself, to learn to manage the school together with representatives of all segments of the school community. This will encourage collegiate bodies to become active, taking over, together with the school management, the administrative and pedagogical process of the school institution.

In this way, the entire school community is committed to the performance of the school, both in the pedagogical and administrative spheres. The director no longer acts alone, but promotes his actions in a dialogic perspective, pointing to the construction of democratic instances of deliberation, such as school councils, student unions, thus guaranteeing the exercise of power sharing.

Of the wide range of activities that are incumbent upon the school director, the role of articulator and encourager of the construction and participation of collegiate actions at school stands out. The collegiate bodies make possible and harmonize the discussion process with teachers, employees, students and students’ parents, allowing actions regarding the school’s problems to be taken together, pointing to democratic solutions.

2.3 POLITICAL-PEDAGOGICAL PROJECT

Professor Cury (2005 , p.11), discussing the importance of the role of the democratic manager in the school, emphasizes that the provision of quality teaching presupposes professional quality as well. And, according to him, this process begins with the elaboration of the pedagogical project, which must have the participation of education professionals who work within the school institution.

Therefore, the management of the pedagogical project is a collective task of the teaching staff, led by the manager in charge, and is aimed at

obtaining another constitutional principle of national education, which is the guarantee of the quality standard. [...] Democratic management as a principle of national education, mandatory presence in public school institutions, is the dialogic, participatory way in which the educational community is able to carry out a quality pedagogical project and from which active citizens are born, society participants as committed professionals. (CURY, 2005, p.11).

These statements made by Cury (2005, p.11) provoke profound reflections on public education and its relations with democratic management. The right to education presupposes a duty of the State. Is this duty being fulfilled in order to provide citizens with quality education? Is the performance of education professionals consistent with what the law determines? In practice, are there really guarantees of access, permanence and quality in public schools?

The elaboration, or re-elaboration, of the Political-Pedagogical Project – PPP of a school must be widely discussed with the school community, prioritizing themes such as access, permanence and quality of public education. Access to school must be allowed without differences or discrimination, with respect to the citizen, so that the right to education effectively takes place.

For Luís Armando Gandin , a quality Political-Pedagogical Project moves towards action, but not just any action, because what matters “[...] is not doing many things, but knowing the reason for each one of the things what we do”. For him, the school’s PPP should not be concerned only with the construction of knowledge, but also with the worldview that underpins this knowledge.

Considering that each school is a particular reality, it is possible to state that the school community of each school constitutes a sample of the different realities that make up society. But what about when we have a school that serves only adolescents in situations of deprivation of liberty? What worldview do they bring to school and what underlies their knowledge? In the vast majority of cases, this teenager is part of school dropout statistics. Designing a pedagogical policy

for this student is a huge challenge for the school.

A political-pedagogical project according to Vasconcelos (2009, p.2) is “[...] the result of the interaction between the objectives and priorities established by the community .” And it is this collectivity that establishes, through reflection, the necessary actions to improve their school. This is the starting point for building a PPP: reflecting on the reality of the school community and outlining the goals to be achieved in order to guarantee quality education.

Veiga (2002 , p.11) emphasizes that quality is centered on the challenge of managing the appropriate instruments for its realization. The political-pedagogical project is an instrument that must be experienced at all times by all those involved with the school’s educational process.

The quality school has an obligation to avoid, in every possible way, repetition and evasion. It has to guarantee the qualitative goal of the satisfactory performance of all. Quality for all, therefore, goes beyond the quantitative goal of global access, in the sense that school-age children enter school. It is necessary to guarantee the permanence of those who enter it. (VEIGA, 2002, p.11).

Therefore, once access to the school is guaranteed, it is also the manager’s function to guarantee the permanence of the student in the school space. The causes of evasion must be investigated with the families. The Statute of the Child and Adolescent provides for the measures to be adopted in defense of the guarantee of the right to education and points out the measures to be adopted if the student does not return to school activities, which includes activating both the Tutelary Council and other sectors that act to protect children and adolescents.

Democratic management and the construction of a political-pedagogical project with the participation of the entire school community are requirements for achieving education for all, a right guaranteed by the Federal Constitution.

2.4 RESEARCH-ACTION

Action research is a methodology that brings together theory, implicit in research, and practice, implicit in action. Applied in social sciences and psychology, action research is now widely used in teaching, where it developed in response to the need to implement educational theory in classroom practice.

Such a method is opposed to traditional research, considered objective, non-reactive, which intends to bring knowledge from the outside in, that is, an external expert brings the news to the person in practice. Action research, on the contrary, makes use of participation, of dialogue, seeking to unite research with practical action.

Engel (2000, p.182/183) states that action research constitutes a means of professional development from the inside out, in which teachers, as professionals in educational practice “[...] instead of being only consumers of research done by others, should turn their own classrooms into objects of research”.

The use of this methodology allows research and action to go hand in hand and, with that, the task of re-elaborating the Political-Pedagogical Project will give a new characteristic to school practice: that of participation.

According to Franco (2005, p.485), action research in Brazil has at least three different concepts: collaborative action research, critical action research and strategic action research. The research is collaborative when the search for transformation is requested by the reference group to the research team; is critical when the need for transformation is felt from the researcher’s work with the group, “[...] resulting from a process that values the cognitive construction of experience, sustained by collective critical reflection”, as stated by Franco (2005, p.485); it is strategic when the transformation is previously planned, and, as Franco (2005, p.486) adds, “[...] without the participation of the subjects, and only the researcher will monitor the effects and evaluate the results of its application”.

2.4.1 Action-Research at School with Students in Socio-Educational Measure

The concept of action-research can be adopted, for example, in a school that assists young teenagers in compliance with a socio-educational measure, and it is expected that the researcher perceives, when contacting the group, its needs . Research along these lines would assume a critical character, aiming at the emancipation of the subjects who interact in the process.

Critical action research considers the subject’s voice, perspective, meaning, but not just for recording and subsequent interpretation by the researcher: the subject’s voice will be part of the fabric of the investigation methodology. (FRANCO, 2005, p. 486).

Within a school with the characteristics mentioned above, where students are deprived of liberty, a question arises in relation to the subject’s voice. Who hears them? Who values the students’ verbalization? Professor Carmem Maria Craidy, in an interview with *Educação e Realidade* magazine (2008, p.2), cites examples of boys serving socio-educational measures who become more disciplined and responsible when coordinators, teachers and police officers talk to them.

Knowing that your voice is heard is feeling valued, individualized in the midst of a large group. Even though they temporarily belong to a segregated group, the contact with other adolescents, with coordinators, employees, police and judges allows these individuals, most of whom come from dysfunctional families, to have contact with discipline, responsibility and to be able to rethink their lives based on this interaction. .

Critical action research, in this situation, will also allow adolescents to be heard, to voice their concerns, talk about their needs and what they think the school can do for them and what they themselves can do. for their education , formal or informal. In discussions with other agents about the formative role of the school, adolescents will be able to assume responsibility for their own school development.

Returning to the Brazilian laws that protect children and adolescents, we have, in 1990,

the institution of the Statute of Children and Adolescents - ECA, but, before that, the Constitution of the Republic of 1988, in its article 227, already defined that

It is the duty of the family, society and the State to assure children and adolescents, with absolute priority, the right to life, health, food, education, leisure, professional training, culture, dignity, respect, to freedom and family and community coexistence, in addition to putting you safe from all forms of negligence, discrimination, exploitation, violence, cruelty and oppression. (BRASIL, 1988)

In the case of adolescents involved in infractions, what we know today as a socio-educational measure did not always exist. In the past, adolescent offenders received care without the intention of educating, only of segregation and punishment. Today the measures have an ethical-pedagogical content guaranteed by the legislation.

The Child and Adolescent Statute, in its article 94, items X and XI, determines that the Inpatient Units have the obligation to provide schooling, professional education, cultural, sports and leisure activities to their inmates. And, in the sole paragraph of article 123, it extends activities of a pedagogical nature to provisional hospitalization as well.

The SINASE – National Monitoring System for Socio-Educational Measures, in its chapter Parameters of Pedagogical Management, points out that socio-educational actions should be aimed at the formation of adolescents in the same conception pointed out by Fortunato (2010, p.1) who puts this adolescent “ [...] as an autonomous and solidary citizen who relates well with himself and with the world and that the socio-educational measure has a legal-sanctionary dimension and a substantial ethical-pedagogical dimension .”

In order to comply with the provisions of the Child and Adolescent Statute, on May 28, 2002, the Foundation for Socio-Educational Assistance (FASE/RS) was born, consolidating the process of institutional reordering of the ECA. The Statute determines differentiated treatment for children

and adolescents who are victims of violence and abandonment and adolescents who commit crimes. FASE specializes in providing exclusive assistance to adolescents who have committed infractions with a judicial measure of confinement or semi-liberty.

The service provided at the Foundation is guided by the National System of Socio-Educational Assistance _ SINASE and by the Program for the Execution of Socio-Educational Measures of Internment and Semiliberty - PEMSEIS, whose main axis is the Individual Assistance Plan. The guarantee of individual and collective rights is the basic assumption of technical and administrative intervention, covering pedagogical and therapeutic aspects in the care of adolescents.

With regard to pedagogical aspects, the schooling of adolescents linked to the school under study is developed by the State Department of Education, coordinated by the 1st CRE – Regional Education Coordination, to which teachers report. Adolescents comply with socio-educational internment measures at the same time that they receive formal education from the State.

In this differentiated school, as recommended by the Rio Grande do Sul State Program for the Execution of Socio-Educational Internment and Semiliberty Measures – PEMSEIS/RS, classes have a maximum of ten students . There is a nine-year elementary education offer, Youth and Adult Education in Elementary Education from the 6th to the 9th grade, and Regular Secondary Education. The school has a graded system, with some multigrade classes.

Students are all male, aged between 12 and 21 years old. The number of enrolled students fluctuates daily, bearing in mind that the turnover of these teenagers is part of the specificity of the school. They show a gap in schooling, age and grade in which they are. Most did not attend school before the deprivation of liberty. According to school enrollments, it appears that a significant number is in the 6th year of elementary school.

Having as a parameter the concept of action-research, when carrying out an intervention-

project for the re-elaboration of the Political-Pedagogical Project of the school in question, it will be necessary that the dialogue involve not only the agents of education, but also the agents of the State that control the Unit where the school operates. The dialogic spiral that action research provides may collide with subjects external to the educational process, since the larger structure of a FASE Unit is directly subordinated to the State Department of Justice. Therefore, a discussion around changes in the school should involve agents of education and also of justice.

Considering the peculiarity of this school, it is possible to state that it still exercises the function of guardianship over the inmates, not being characterized as a school with democratic management, in the conceptual range that this term has. It will be necessary to create open spaces that require State actions directed towards a new reality, that the school is multicultural and this diversity is important for the development of the subjects.

In this sense, the work of the school management comes to be understood as a team process, in the perspective pointed out by Lück, (2000) where there is no longer an awareness of administration, but of school management. And this implies a fundamental change in attitude and conceptual orientation. The first step will be to encourage the participation of adolescents in proposing changes that generate improvements in the school. Include them in the situation analysis process, so that they can decide together, also being agents of change.

From this shared work, guided by the desire to seek improvements, a process of collective construction of an educational space that meets the specific needs of this school community will emerge. It is essential to create participatory environments so that students can build a vision that the school is not a punitive and distant entity, but a space where they can exercise their right to a quality education, which directs them towards total development how to be a citizen.

Formal education is a mandatory part of the socio-educational measure applied to adolescents. As the vast majority of them were out of school, for

different reasons, this legal requirement is seen by them not as a right but as a punishment. At first, there is an evident rejection of school activities. Some have time to change their attitude towards a new proposal presented by the school; others, due to the high turnover in the houses, leave as they entered, believing that schoolwork is punitive and not everyone's right.

In view of this, how can a democratic management process be carried out that permeates the elaboration of the Political-Pedagogical Proposal that counts on the participation of all segments in a school whose public is adolescents in compliance with socio-educational measures without the possibility of external activity?

The pedagogical aspect of schools that operate within FASE units must include the generation of opportunities that, after complying with the socio-educational measure, can "... provide a better life perspective for these young people", as stated by Pereira (2013 , p.1).

This is the challenge envisioned from this course. To present a participatory school that can be seen by the student as their right, a possibility to improve their quality of life. New knowledge can generate in these adolescents other perspectives and meanings for school education, allowing social reintegration after fulfilling the socio-educational measure.

3 FINAL CONSIDERATIONS

I conclude the work by presenting, as final considerations, the possibility of applying an intervention project that takes into account the different reality of the school where I work, whose main characteristic lies in the public served: adolescents in deprivation of liberty, fulfilling socio-educational measures.

According to research coordinated by Professor Craidy (2008), half of the adolescents who are serving socio-educational measures are out of school, due to abandonment, and come from dysfunctional families. Setting up a school council within the units would bring these families closer to their children's school reality, showing

the importance that family monitoring has on children's development, both in the affective field and in the field of knowledge.

This approximation, however, would need to be accompanied by social workers and health professionals, such as psychologists and therapists. A joint effort that could reach the offender teenager and also the families who, for various reasons, could not closely monitor the development of their children. Any improvement in these relationships would be a gain for those involved in the process.

A research coordinated by Professor Craidy (2008) points out that the coordinators of the houses that receive teenagers in compliance with a socio-educational measure claim that such measures produce some positive effect on a portion of the hospitalized teenagers. They conclude that 18.7% of adolescents are positively influenced by the effect of discipline; 17.3%, due to the impact of responsibility; and 13.3% for the effect caused by the organization.

The logic of time in these places has its own characteristic. These adolescents meet different periods of permanence in the institution. Teachers who work in these schools need to think about different work strategies that address these specific issues. The pedagogical projects have to be of a determined time, in view of the high turnover of students.

A project may cover a maximum period of two months. The evaluations must be done in a procedural way, for each topic, since on the next day one or several students may have been transferred or returned home. The teacher needs to promote reception practices, collective dialogue, differentiated service, seeking to recover values, self-esteem, limits, rights and duties of students.

We are aware that an action-research, to be carried out, needs time and space for each person involved in the process to appropriate the new concepts and build what they want to see changed in their school reality.

Bearing in mind the specificities of the school

under study, and the constant rotation of students, the research could be carried out in the same space, but with different subjects. Although they have the same condition as inmates for offenses committed, it is understood that the needs of each one are different, because man is multiple and diverse by his nature as a human being.

Even in this unique situation, we envision the possibility of preparing a project to discuss with the school community actions aimed at improving the school, thinking about the development of students as a whole.

This perspective that school management can provide dialogue and interaction between education professionals, students and the community arises from participation in the Doctoral Course in Education Sciences at UNIDA University. The theoretical framework made available in the Course enabled us to learn a great deal in the area of school management. This knowledge made it possible to bring about changes in the school routine and in the pedagogical work of the teachers, who felt encouraged to review their pedagogical practices, aiming at better use and learning by the students. We believe that more significant changes can be achieved if it is possible to forward an intervention project that discusses, with the school community and the Department of Justice, practical alternatives aimed at improving the student-school-community relationship in schools that operate within the Units of the Foundation for Socio-Educational Service of the State of Rio Grande do Sul.

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PSYCHO-PEDAGOGICAL INTERVENTION: STUDY DEVELOPED AT THE FRANCISCAN HIGHER EDUCATION INSTITUTE OF PAÇO DO LUMIAR, MA

AUTHORS

Lizilene Araújo Neves Saldanha - Master in Educational Sciences from the University of Sol - Unades/PY, Specialist in Psychopedagogy from FACI - Faculdade Ideal Belém-PA, Graduated in Pedagogy from the State University of Pará-UEPA.

ABSTRACT

This present article aims to present the case study carried out at the Instituto de Ensino Superior Franciscano (IESF, private college) and its approaches to the Psychopedagogy and continuing education relevance for psycho-pedagogues participating in the Psychopedagogical Intervention Social Project (ProSIPp), developed in the institution. This study sought to answer the following question: Does ProSIPp allow other perspective use to define the psycho-pedagogue professional praxis? Does the psycho-pedagogue strengthen its intervention practices through participation in the project? The proposed objective was to inquire about the ProSIPp influence in the psychopedagogists continuing education process, through the theories and practices acquired arising from psychopedagogical interventions was seen as a professional profile development. All psycho-pedagogues who participated in the project from 2017 to 2019, making a total of 24 and the selected sample was 50%, which corresponds to 12 psycho-pedagogues who were corresponded by the research universe. It was possible to perceive the ProSIPp social role importance by its results, which contributed satisfactorily to the difficulties minimization related to learning and also provided a new vision of the psychopedagogist profession, which needs to be improved regarding the knowledge in the area advances to assist those who need help in building learning better.

Keywords: Psychopedagogy. Psychopedagogical service. ProSIPp. IESF.

INTRODUCTION

Psychopedagogy is an area of knowledge that deals with the human learning process, having the human being itself as the object of study, in the apprehension of reality and the construction of knowledge. Psychopedagogy studies the teaching-learning process and its difficulties, mainly related to pedagogical practice, involving meeting individual and group needs, learning, school failure and appropriation of knowledge by the subject.

Concerned with the diversity of courses, the Brazilian Association of Psychopedagogy (ABPp) has been vehemently discussing topics related to the training of this professional, such as the identity of the Psychopedagogue, the recognition of activities, the legitimacy of the social action of Psychopedagogy, among others.

Deepening the understanding of Psychopedagogy has become relevant as one also seeks to understand the relevance of continuing education for professionals in the area. Thus, the following proposal arose: "FROM TRAINING TO PSYCHO-PEDAGOGICAL INTERVENTION: a study based on the Social Project of Psycho-pedagogical Intervention (ProSIPp) developed at the Franciscan Higher Education Institute in Paço do Lumiar-MA". The Instituto de Ensino Superior Franciscano (IESF) is located in Maiobão, in the municipality of Paço do Lumiar-MA, which for seven years has been gradually undergoing a reformulation of its curriculum design, trying to follow the guidelines set out in the Education Guidelines for Psychopedagogues in Brazil, from the moment in which the HEI is concerned with the training of its students, when it offers supervised practice in its course structure, called Supervised Internship, which includes a psycho-pedagogical evaluation and the desire to detail about the constitution and development of the Social Project for Psychopedagogical Intervention (ProSIPp), whose focus is to contribute to the post-training of newly graduated students from the IES Psychopedagogy Course, thus extending psycho-pedagogical intervention to the surrounding community, children and adolescents from public schools or private, previously evaluated and diagnosed in the internship, with learning difficulties.

To carry out the study and carry out the proposal

contained in this project, it will be necessary to use two methodological mechanisms: Bibliographic Research and the Case Study. To answer the question proposed in the project, the following procedures will be followed: analysis of the ProSIPp documentation and study of the actions developed by the ProSIPp. The research universe corresponds to all psycho-pedagogues who participated in the project from 2017 to 2019, making a total of 24. And the selected sample will be 50%, which corresponds to 12 psycho-pedagogues.

The research aims to deepen the understanding of Psychopedagogy, making it essential, as it also seeks to understand the relevance of continuing education for newly formed psychopedagogues. The general objective of the research was to inquire about the influence of ProSIPp in the psychopedagogue's continuing education process and to develop a professional profile based on the acquisition of theories and practices resulting from psycho-pedagogical interventions.

The research interest is reinforced by the desire to present the ProSIPp, developed at the Instituto de Ensino Superior Franciscano (IESF), considering its multiple relevance in the fields of psycho-pedagogical assistance, in the continuing education of educational psychologists and social responsibility.

APPROACH TO PSYCHO PEDAGOGY

When mentioning the advent of Psychopedagogy, we bring the writings of Pain (2012), which clarifies that even today, one of the difficult problems for Pedagogy is the relationship between the construction of knowledge by the individual and the constitution of the subject through knowledge. The author emphasizes that Pedagogy, at the time, did not take into account the individual and his history, his destiny, something that differentiated him from other individuals, that is, his uniqueness. In Rubinstein's writings (2012, p. 15), she emphasizes the following:

Long before talking about Psychopedagogy, Special Education, Therapeutic Pedagogy, and Re-education, there was already news of educational experiences aimed at specific situations that involved limitations in the learning

of an organic or even social nature.

The author continues by stating that the activities were developed, sometimes intuitively, by educators who had idealism and utopia as flags. In this way, from humanists, romantics and idealists, specialized educators became re-educators, specialists in the treatment of learning problems. One of the treatment objectives was to prove the efficiency of tests applied to schoolchildren within a given testing period.

Given the procedures adopted, the words of Rubinstein (2012) undoubtedly confirm this is a caricatured and synthetic view of re-education. And, he continues “probably, many more sensitive re-educators, intuitively, did not limit themselves to administering tests and proposing series of exercises, focusing their attention on the subject. For her, the positive results of the tests occurred due to the insistence and belief in the possibilities for human beings to change.

Such insistence and belief, originated from dreamers, idealists, and non-conformists, who have always existed in all areas, says Rubinstein (2012). As proof, it brings, among others, the figure of Ann Sullivan, who, out of idealism, was willing to bring about changes where they were little expected. That is, they reached out to people who, for different reasons, were socially marginal. Therefore, the author points out that it is possible to believe that re-educators, due to their profile of dreamers, had a great capacity to deal with the limits and frustrations arising from the dramatic conditions they faced.

Based on Rubinstein’s statement (2012) about idealistic educators and their attitudes towards the care provided to socially disadvantaged children, and that this attitude gave rise to the positive results of the applied tests, consequently, transformations emerged. The changes, or rather the transformations, began with the arrival of the 20th century, even with therapeutic interventions in the medical/pedagogical approach, with a view to re-education, focusing on a certain clientele. In this case, re-education centres were built for child offenders. This time, it appears in the literary context, not only in Europe, but the United

States, both with the following history: “In the United States and Europe, the number of private schools and individualized teaching for children considered to be slow learners is growing”. (BOSSA, 2011, p. 59).

For Rubinstein (2012) re-education could become Psychopedagogy when it embraced and built a broader ideological platform on the concept of learning, using a multidisciplinary view. For the author, in Psychopedagogy, the fundamental thing is to know and understand the learning process, to understand the learning difficulty from it. According to her, this assumption contributes to modifying the understanding of the etiology of learning difficulties, as well as the modality of intervention.

In his exposition, Rubinstein presents the definition of learning elaborated by Dabas (1998), for judging it to be quite clear. As he goes on to mention that learning is the process by which a subject, in his interaction with the environment, incorporates the information offered by this environment, according to his needs and interests”. (DABAS, 1998 apud RUBINSTEIN, 2012).

In this sense, he goes on to state that this happens: He elaborates this information through his psychic structure, constituted by the social interplay, the dynamics of the unconscious and the cognitive dynamics, modifying his behaviour to accept new proposals and carry out unprecedented transformations in the environment that surrounds him. (DABAS, 1998 apud RUBINSTEIN, 2012).

Following the historical context, let’s see what is the definition of the object of study of psychopedagogy according to some theorists:

The objective of the psycho-pedagogical treatment is the disappearance of the symptom and the possibility for the subject to learn normally in better conditions, emphasizing the relationship that he may have with learning, that is, that the subject is the agent of his learning and that he appropriates of knowledge. (PAIN

apud ARAGÃO, 2010, p. 21).

Scoz and Barone (apud ARAGÃO, 2010, p. 22) define: “[...] psychopedagogy as an area that studies and deals with the learning process and its difficulties and that in a professional action, it must encompass several fields of knowledge, integrating and systematizing them”.

These different meanings related to psychopedagogy tell us about a process that is being structured, and whose identity is maturing. As Macedo states (apud ARAGÃO, 2010, p. 34), “[...] psychopedagogy is a (new) area of professional activity that seeks an identity that requires training at an interdisciplinary level”. Currently, even as an area of knowledge, Psychopedagogy deals with the human learning process, having the human being itself as the object of study, in the apprehension of reality and the construction of knowledge.

Psychopedagogy studies the teaching-learning process and its difficulties, mainly related to pedagogical practice, envisioning how the subject relates affectively, cognitively, pedagogically and socially with learning. Respecting this subject's need for care in individual and group circumstances, paying attention to their learning modality, to minimize or solve the difficulty of learning. This difficulty, which may be related to internal and/or external factors to the learner, is sometimes addressed to school failure.

According to Escott (2004 apud ARAGÃO, 2010), in the psycho-pedagogical diagnosis, it is necessary to identify, in the subject's development and in the relationship with his family and social groups in which he lives, the meaning of non-learning. Thus, Clinical Psychopedagogy starts from the subject's personal history, seeking to identify their learning modality and understand the message of other subjects involved in this process, be it the family or the school, seeking, implicitly or not, the causes of not learning. Emphasizing the clinical approach, the author stresses that it goes through an intense process of investigation into the intriguing factors of the subject's non-learning, which is called psycho-pedagogical diagnosis.

Linked to Bossa's thinking on psycho-pedagogical diagnosis, for Weiss (2016) what is important in this process is the perception of the individual way each person learns and produces. In pursuit of understanding learning difficulties and the factors that can lead to school failure.

Still on the clinical approach, Bossa (2011) points out that clinical work takes place through the relationship between personal history and the learning modality. It is of fundamental importance that the psycho-pedagogue professional can identify how the subject is constituted, what transformations he has undergone throughout the different stages of life, what structures and concepts he has built and how he relates to knowledge. Therefore, it becomes necessary for the clinical psycho-pedagogue to assume it as a duty, not only to seek to understand why the subject has a certain learning difficulty, but how he can learn and how this learning process will take place. This understanding will begin in the diagnostic process, as latent desires for learning are released by the learning subject, thus allowing for this understanding.

As pointed out above, the diagnosis is the starting point for psycho-pedagogical investigation. However, it is worth mentioning that, in the sense of evolution, affirmation and support of Psychopedagogy, the Techniques of Psychopedagogical Diagnosis have been improving, opening space for reflection to psychopedagogues, on the procedures adopted in their modality of performance.

Facing this manifestation, Rubinstein (2001, p. 24) emphasizes: If, in the re-education approach, what is in evidence as an object of research is the failure as a deviation, in the dynamic psychopedagogy approach, it is intended to understand the failures within the perspective of the subject of learning, that is, understanding and raising possible hypotheses for this deviation or this unsatisfactory relationship with knowledge and knowledge.

When thinking about Psychopedagogy in the Brazilian context, it is admitted that in Brazil, there

are two paths to follow, in the search for training in Psychopedagogy, at the undergraduate and Post-Graduate *Latu Sensu* levels. Regarding the latter, in the modalities: face-to-face, blended and distance learning, with different workloads. The *Latu Sensu* format stands out in terms of offering more courses, for this reason, specialization must be considered as a starting point in the training of psycho-pedagogues in Brazil.

Continuing the thought above, Serrano (2001 apud PERES, 2014) among other words informs that training in Psychopedagogy is taking place, in general, in *Latu Sensu* Postgraduate courses, linked to educational institutions that meet the requirements established by the National Board of Education.

About the formation of psychopedagogues in Brazil, it has always been a concern of those who headed Psychopedagogy to establish itself in Brazil, since the foundation of the State Association of Psychopedagogues of São Paulo (AEP), whose objective was to work on the professional profile, the field of performance and the formation of the psychopedagogue. (BARONE, 2020). Even before the AEP, there were already meetings between the members of the group that constituted it. In the meetings they discussed, and each time they advanced the identity, role and field of action of the psycho-pedagogue. Between the lines, words from Noffs (2003, p. 58). As for the time, Rubinstein (2020, p. 27) reinforces: "Continuing education, deepening and interest in innovations in the educational and psycho-pedagogical field were our priorities". Rubinstein (2020) emphasizes that at the time of the AEP, young psychopedagogues used to work together, despite the commissions. Thus, he recalls: "At each Board meeting we asked ourselves: What does a psychopedagogue do? What is Psychopedagogy? The reduced steering group, composed of a maximum of 20 professional colleagues from different backgrounds and interests, shared knowledge". (RUBINSTEIN, 2020, p. 27).

GETTING TO KNOW THE SOCIAL PROJECT OF PSYCHO-PEDAGOGICAL INTERVENTION (PROSIPp)

The research institution of this study is the Instituto de Ensino Superior Franciscano (IESF) located in the municipality of Paço do Lumiar/MA, which maintains the Integrated Center for Pedagogical and Psychopedagogical Monitoring and Management (NIGApp), which is a psychopedagogical support service and psychological to academics and professors of undergraduate and graduate courses at the HEI, in face-to-face and distance learning modalities. The NIGApp is a space that brings together different services that are available to teachers/tutors and students of *Latu Sensu* Undergraduate and Postgraduate Courses, as well as monitors and supports the Course Coordination, Distance Learning Coordination and the Evaluation Commission, in monitoring all actions to support the needs identified throughout the process, aiming at improving individual and/or collective performance. The Social Project of Psychopedagogical Intervention (ProSIPp), will also contribute to the level of improvement of the practice in psychopedagogy for students coming from the Psychopedagogy Course, thus, ProSIPp starts its activities in 2016, given a year of observation that generated many concerns in the researcher. Concerns arose around the significant demand of children and adolescents participating in the internship with hypotheses of difficulties in learning to read, write and calculate. As well as meeting the aspirations of students completing the aforementioned course, extending their studies and continuing their practical work in Psychopedagogy.

DATA ANALYSIS AND DISCUSSION

This section presents the results obtained in the case study based on the analysis of the information contained in the data collection instrument. When asked about their knowledge of ProSIPp, the sample was unanimous in responding that it had access to the project during the supervised internship, in the Specialization Course in Psychopedagogy at IESF. The project intends to cover the following target audience: "Learners evaluated in the Supervised Internship in Psychopedagogy, as well as their families, psychopedagogues and volunteer monitors and Internship Supervisor". (IESF, 2016, p. 1).

I got to know ProSIPp during the internship discipline of the Specialization Course in Institutional and Clinical Psychopedagogy, offered by the Instituto de Ensino Superior Franciscano-IESF. At first, through the teacher's exposition about this project and later, during the development of the internship in the same place where the project was developed. In this space, there was a panel with images and small texts that validated the activities developed in ProSIPp. (INTERVIEWEE).

The above mention goes against the data obtained since the project is disclosed to the students of the postgraduate course in Psychopedagogy of the IESF, at the time of the supervised internship, which constitutes the last three disciplines of the course, it is also disclosed in the institution's digital media so that the announcement can reach the knowledge of the graduates of the said course. The question below deals with the description of how that phase was, as ProSIPp has two distinct phases: a theoretical phase and a practical phase.

ProSIPp in 2019 returned with a new theoretical and methodological perspective. The project aimed to work on reading and writing in a dialogical perspective, through textual genres. To this end, the first step was to re-elaborate the ProSIPp work project based on the study of theorists who were aligned with this proposal. In the second moment, the training meetings were designed based on this reference and with this reference. Therefore, reading the selected material was a key factor in this process, not just any reading, but a reflective reading that resulted in records of the texts read. (INTERVIEWEE).

The study phase of the project was described by the psycho-pedagogues as an important phase because it brought explanations about the methodologies used by the psycho-pedagogue,

at the time that dialogue circles and exchange of experience about what was read were held. In this calm process and mediated by the ProSIPp coordinator, who always coordinated the discussions, the group's intellectual enrichment happened. The study addressed several theorists who in the future would help in the intervention process.

The theoretical phase comprises every part of the study that is developed by the project members, through meetings, studies of specialized texts and deepening on renowned theorists. This phase allows reflection and study with emphasis on the perception of the object of psychopedagogy and its manifestation. The study on the methodologies and instruments of psychopedagogy is also included, aiming at future intervention.

About the execution, the project started with a planning meeting with the project coordination, there was a welcome for the Psychopedagogues who worked on the project.

Regarding the development of the project, the following actions can be mentioned:

[...] the dossier of each learner is read, received by the students and family members responsible, then the intervention sessions begin with specific materials and instruments according to the needs of the students, evaluation of the practice and adjustments in the planning when necessary and they give back to families. (INTERVIEWEE).

Continuing with the reports, one of the interviewees reported that the project was carried out on Tuesdays, by two volunteer psychopedagogues, which took place from 6:30 pm to 7:50 pm (1 hour and 20 minutes duration) for the service time. There were 20 meetings interspersed with group studies.

This phase was identified as very productive and challenging, as there were 2 groups of customers, each with its specificities. The first moment was the contact with the families and clients, in which dynamics were carried out with them to have

the first observations, from there, sessions were carried out based on the diagnosis of each one, being based on the project proposal on Genders Literary, in which fairy tales, fables, riddles, letters, etc. were worked on... Following a didactic sequence in each session about the genres worked on.

The project was carried out in pairs, and initially, we found out about the complaints brought by the families/school, through the files/files of each client, so that we could carry out an assertive intervention in each identified learning difficulty. We sought to find out whether, during the development of the project, there was a need to use classic instruments of Psychopedagogy learned during the training in Psychopedagogy, and as answers projective tests, operative tests, drawings, various games, toys, and games were cited according to the age range and difficulty observed by each client. Piagetian proofs and the projective techniques used were recurrent in the intervention process to confirm or disqualify previous readings made in the process. For example, the projective technique A Planta da Casa was used to confirm hypotheses raised during the internship evaluation service.

The intervention took place through textual genres, games, reading workshops, production of stories (autobiography, short stories, poems) through posters and others, activities in the toy library, and activities that involved feelings (self-esteem) with the use of plaques with positive messages and emojis. (INTERVIEWEE).

It was emphasized that psycho-pedagogical games were made, activities were organized that favoured the learning of learners according to needs, in addition, medical records were organized to develop the intervention plan. The next question was whether, during participation in the project, there was the elaboration of any instrument(s) based on the diagnosed reality and which ones, where it was informed that instruments aimed at literacy were used, such as pairing, rhyme, reading pyramid, syllable stripes among others. Also cited were:

group diary, group life book, conversation wheel and others.

On the influence of ProSIPp in strengthening the professional identity of the Psychopedagogue, in addition to seeking if there was understanding about the psycho-pedagogical work.

Regarding the question: According to your perception, how does ProSIPp influence the strengthening of the Psychopedagogue's professional identity? There is the following analysis: The ProSIPp influences the identity of the psycho pedagogue when it allows the newly graduated in psychopedagogy the opportunity to continue with assistance and studies, as this way we acquire more experience about the psycho-pedagogical practice. The ProSIPp through the studies provided the perception that there are factors that interfere with the student's learning. The ProSIPp enables psycho-pedagogues to experience psycho-pedagogical practice supervised by more experienced Psychopedagogues and guided by a theoretical-methodological framework in a space of action with real demands, something scarce in the Metropolitan Region of São Luís. This perspective of training enables psycho-pedagogues to experience training which makes them safer in their performance.

It enabled the exercise of work activity more autonomously and safely, allowing doubts to be resolved and professional identity strengthened mainly through observation and the search for knowledge, through scientific research. The project provided the Psychopedagogue with first contact with his role, thus searching for his identity according to his performance/practice.

The answers allow us to state how much the ProSIPp had a positive impact on the training and professional identity of the psycho-pedagogues who participated in the project, the following report can be presented:

The importance of having a holistic view of the subject; The importance of listening to all subjects who are involved with the development of the learning subject; Organization, planning, commitment and study are essential;

you can learn from everyone, always. The psycho-pedagogical intervention is something serious, it can harm the development of the learner if it is not taken seriously by the professionals responsible for promoting learning. (INTERVIEWEE).

Other aspects were mentioned as a guarantee to the community of professional subsidies in the psycho-pedagogical field that made possible the change in the educational scenario, by minimizing learning difficulties through psycho-pedagogical assistance.

The physical space, resources and theoretical support ensured a cohesive work, with rich learning possibilities for the psychopedagogue's personal and professional life. It is possible here to highlight other aspects considered relevant: it prepares one to analyze and understand the cause of learning difficulty, it enables one to reflect on what instruments one can use to overcome the difficulty, it develops creativity and an innovative spirit, it encourages research and looking for theorists who advise which paths to follow, sensitizes to seek activities that promote the self-esteem of clients and generating new knowledge. This analysis made it possible to verify that the project provided training and learning opportunities for new Psychopedagogues, as well as contributed to the intervention process of low-income people in the community and fulfilled the objective of seeking to give a positive response to the client in the face of the problems that are facing related to their children's learning.

About the professional profile, based on participation in the project: The results of the research demonstrate that there was a learning experience in terms of taking better care of the psycho-pedagogical work, investing in training and resources, being more cautious, exercising better listening and also in learning about looking at the subject instead of their conflicting situations.

There was a re-dimensioning of the professional profile, because before, some interviewees considered their knowledge in the field of

psychopedagogy incipient, and now they are stronger professionals able to extend a hand to a child, or an adolescent, who will investigate what is affecting their learning and will find alternatives to overcome these difficulties. But I know I still have a lot to learn.

[...] Even with experience in other spaces, I still didn't feel safe acting. My biggest concern has always been the lack of a theoretical framework and the mix of theorists that many psycho-pedagogues used to support their work. Through the project, I was able to study theorists who provided answers to my concerns and challenges experienced in psycho-pedagogical work. (INTERVIEWEE).

It was possible to perceive the importance of the social role, to contribute satisfactorily to the minimization of difficulties related to learning. There was a new vision of the psycho-pedagogue profession, which needs to be up to date with knowledge and advances in the area to better assist those who need help in the construction of learning. Participation in the project was identified as an excellent experience, which opened the horizons of what is needed to develop a work of excellence in the area.

FINAL CONSIDERATIONS

Thinking about the strengthening of Psychopedagogy through continuing education, I suggest that HEIs with specialization courses in Psychopedagogy offer former students the possibility of insertion in an extension project, as a proposal for continuing education. Where the former student, now a professional, finds in this possibility, conditions to outline his practice, deepening his knowledge, and through the use of other lenses, encourage himself to use new resources and/or instruments in psycho-pedagogical intervention.

Therefore, the training proposal envisages the maintenance of a teaching and learning sequence, relating theory to practice, favouring the encouragement of recent graduates to face the job market.

Based on fifteen years of professional experience in Psychopedagogy, for nine years Psychopedagogy has been working in the social dimension, when it seeks knowledge, through socio-educational action, believing that learning takes place in the institution, whether educational or family, articulating the accumulated experience with what is present.

From this perspective, the Social Project of Psychopedagogical Intervention (ProSIPp) is born, which is developed within an HEI, serving schools, families, and students, reminiscent of a psycho-pedagogical evaluation process, which includes the practice of the Specialization Course of the Institute of Higher Education Franciscano (IESF), located in the municipality of Paço do Lumiar-MA.

Given the study's exposition, it is believed that the training structure of the HEI in question meets the principles of the ABPP, regarding the training and post-training of the psychopedagogue in Brazil, when the IESF, guarantees in its staff, a psychopedagogical professional, to meet and pay attention to the evolutionary needs of their course and consequently accompany the students in the disciplines of Psychopedagogical Practice, called Supervised Internship, which takes place in a proper, equipped and healthy environment.

The institution that hosted the research was the Instituto de Ensino Superior Franciscano (IESF), and one of the criteria was due to the concern with the provision of continuing education to its former students, through extension projects, which allow practical tests that favour the intertwine between theory and practice to strengthen future performance as a professional. After explaining the same exposed in this study and the conclusions, we present here the recommendations for ProSIPp to continue its educational and social contribution, collaborating with the development of the region it serves. It is important to point out that the project, as it has been developed to date, had a positive impact on the educational context of many children and on strengthening the professional identity of the educational psychologists who participated in the

project. The analysis made through the collected data shows that the project is on the right path. In this way, the recommendations mentioned below, aim to contribute to the expansion of the project, leaving the IESF with the study and viability of them.

That the institution can expand the ProSIPp, guaranteeing its growth through: increasing the number of vacancies proposed in the Notices, considering that the demand and need for psychopedagogical assistance is real and the NIGAPP has a growing demand, ideally that more vacancies with a view to meeting the demand specified above; celebration of agreements with educational institutions, these agreements seek partnerships, thinking in the context of basic education and that the Project can serve more children; expansion of the physical space, the intention is to maximize the service by having a wider and more adequate space; creation of the "ProSIPp na Escola" project, as a result of the pandemic, people began to think about a way to implement the project, where children did not need to go to the IESF to be assisted; that the IESF can create a repository of knowledge through the productions generated from it, such as reports, reports and articles; that NIGAPP institute an annual event with ProSIPp productions.

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STUDY ON THE SUSTAINABILITY AND MANAGEMENT OF MANAGEMENT OF SMALL HOTELS: IN RELATION TO THE ENVIRONMENT IN CALDAS NOVAS (GO), FROM 2015 TO 2020

AUTHORS

Ronaldo do Nascimento Carvalho: Post Doctorate in Administration by UNIBE/PY; PhD in Education Sciences from the Columbia University of Paraguay and Master in the Graduate Program in Non- -Closed Cultural Territories and Expressions (TECCER).

Joana D'arc Bardella Castro: Teacher at the State University of Goiás, postgraduate program in Territories and Cultural Expressions in the Cerrado - TECCER and Natural Resources of the Cerrado – RENAC, Brazil

ABSTRACT

The present work brings about the management and its relationship with the environment in the years 2015 to 2020 of the inns in Caldas Novas, which is a municipality of Goiás that has a very high economic development driven by the growth of the large urban centers of the state. Naturally, this locality mixes local customs and, thought, mainly, in the form of organization of the tourist places, that is, appropriation of the urban spaces, mainly, population. It is possible to state that, through the modernization engendered in capitalist production, this territory has had a tourist dynamic that, due to this, managers have difficulties that cause the visible and disturbing impact in this region. The general objective is to analyze the management and its relationship with the environment in the years 2015 to 2020 of the inns in Caldas Novas. While the methodology is of a qualitative and quantitative approach, based on bibliographical, documentary and field research, using resources from books, articles, magazines, theses, dissertations, legislation, among other materials on Caldas Novas, found at the base of the Google Scholar and publications site related to the topic. As for the results, the surveys had their objectives achieved, showing that tourist activities and the management of inns have great responsibilities in the environmental impacts, based on the analyzes raised in these sectors. Finally, it is concluded that the constant significant increase of visitors, in Caldas Novas, causes the inns to be overcrowded, overloading their basic services, noting that this floating population starts to provide an increase in demand that results in the degradation local. However, it is summarized that tourist activities directly affect this municipality, harming the daily lives of residents of this city, considering that the management of these establishments is primarily responsible for negative experiences in this territory.

Keyword: Caldas Novas. Inn. Management. Environment..

INTRODUCTION

Caldas Novas is a municipality in the State of Goiás that has a high economic development, as shown by numbers exposed in IBGE (2023), driven by the growth of the state's large urban centers. Naturally, this locality mixes local customs and, thought, mainly, in the form of organization of the tourist places, that is, appropriation of the urban spaces, mainly, population.

It is possible to state that, through the modernization engendered in capitalist production, this territory has had a tourist dynamic that, due to this, managers have difficulties in adapting to compliance with environmental legislation in view of the progress on the rise, which causes the impact in that region.

Two factors contributed greatly to the settlement of the region: the thermal waters and gold that was plentiful on the banks of the stream of caldas, at the time called stream of lavras. Enthusiastic with the source of hot water, Martinho Coelho took up residence there, also keeping an eye on the gold mines that were multiplying: he took over a vast tract of land in the locality and built Sítio das Caldas, then requested the sesmária (right of possession) of the lands, legalizing their properties, where he dedicated himself to gold mining. Soon the news of the existence of gold and the medicinal value of the waters spread, attracting hundreds of outsiders and sick people, who built shacks on the banks of the stream of lavras (JESUS, 2016, p. 02).

In view of this, the tourist activities of Caldas Novas began to gain new reflections by constituting spaces with greater emphasis on diversities that vary from the main attractions of leisure, education and recreation, such as, for example, the Parque Estadual da Serra that in the last 50 years expose a reality with activities related to ecotourism (SANTOS; BARBOSA; MENDONÇA, 2020).

Therefore, the main objective of the study is to understand the relationship between the problem and the relationship between the management of local-based inns in Caldas Novas and the incidence of problems caused to the environment in the years 2015 to 2020 and the way in which these can

respond to the demands current.

The article starts from the elementary assumption whose basis is structured in the bibliographical review aimed at explaining and understanding the performance with regard to the protection of the environment, its correlated legislation with support from field research. The central axis of the dissertation focuses on the expectation of receptivity of these norms and the impact on the structure of the family bonded inn, more traditional in Caldas Novas/GO.

The premise of the research rests on the justification of the permanence or not of these establishments by environmental dictates, in view of the emergence of large tourist complexes that offer better conditions and visibility to attract tourists from different regions of the country. At this point, small inns have more difficulties, as they are more restricted to the surrounding public, unknown nationwide. This difficulty has to be revisited in order to understand whether the core business of the commercial establishment can or cannot survive in the face of the currently imposed guidelines.

However, all tourist dynamics and the high investment destined for economic production cause changes in urban spaces, since all this represents visible impacts in Caldas Novas, which, due to tourist attractions, results in a high potential for the exploitation of natural resources. Nevertheless, it is noted that population growth resides in urban spaces, presenting new behaviors that began to show themselves in demographic transformations and, thus, new forms of landscapes, in particular, the local environment.

PRESENTATION OF DATA SURVEYS

Descriptive, bibliographical and field research with a quantitative approach. The data collection instrument will be done through the application of a questionnaire with the managers of the inns in the main thermal tourist destination of the cerrado.

The sample was non-probabilistic. As inclusion criteria, it was composed of representatives (owner or manager) of inns in the city of Caldas Novas (GO), who participated in the 2019 Hotel Census. Exclusion criteria will include representatives of

inns who do not sign the TCLE.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

It was asked if there was knowledge of the execution of tourist projects whose purpose is to integrate the local community and the tourism activity and the answers were presented as follows: 11 (eleven) participants claimed to have no knowledge, only 2 (two) claimed to have knowledge and 4 (four) refused to participate in the research, totaling 17 (seventeen) as informed in the previous item.

According to Santos et. al., (2020), in Caldas Novas/GO, there are numerous tourist activities throughout the year, in which it could create tourist projects, contemplating, through resources, the expansion of the offer of local attractions that favor the integration of the local community, in order to generate more jobs, income and regional development. Above all, it has been perceived that this region has a demand that expands several sectors that are linked to tourism, such as, for example, restaurants, inns, among others, which are indirectly supplying the needs of the economic segment of this region. Therefore, it is necessary to develop planning through public will, private initiative and civil society itself.

It was asked if the inn participated in any promotion aimed at protecting the tourist, artistic and historical heritage of the municipality of Caldas Novas and it was possible to verify that 7 (seven) participants said they participated and 5 (five) said they did not participate and the others, refused to answer.

Complementing this question and the responses of the interviewees, it is clear that the relationship with the research comes from the precariousness of the promotion and destruction of the inns that, with the emergence of large complexes, did not follow the evolution of time and legal regulations:

People from outside started building inns, the natives started selling their land, handing over the land to them, and the movement grew and then for that reason it harmed the traditional people of the place a lot, because they

were taking up space. [Tourism started to arrive here when?] Tourism based on about 8 years when it started to grow tourism here; then they found out that the place was beautiful, that the people were preserving a lot and they started to arrive. Then these people from outside, the businessmen, started to create an eye and started building inns and then the people started to lose their tradition, their rights, so tourism in that sense is a little detrimental. Because the following: before we did the tourism in these small boats, with canoes, on the river, earning their money, selling something that was better sold on the coast, the tourists sought out the native people more, so we made money with that. And not now. There are the inns and they stay there, with their packages, they already do their things there, directly at the inns. So tourists don't leave anything with families. They stay there, what they have to drink they drink there, what they have to eat they eat there at the inns. Boat trips, the inns already have a boat to go on trips, so people are selling [...] (TURISMO EM FOCO, 2019, p. 50-51).

In line with the author's citation, this report was based on a response to the interviewees' narratives. Seeking, in this way, to prove that most inns do not participate in the protection of the tourist, artistic and historical heritage of the municipality of Caldas Novas, allowing reflections that reinforce the lack of environmental protection in this municipality (TURISMO EM FOCO, 2019).

Then, it was asked if the local tourism bodies value the didactics of having criteria to configure the smart destination. In view of this statement, the following options were presented: Totally Agree, Moderately Agree, Totally Disagree, Moderately Disagree and Undecided. The answers given are presented according to graph.

Graph Intelligent Tourist Destinations of Caldas Novas in the year 2022

Source: Data from the researcher (2022).

Observing the responses in the graph above, it is noted that there is greater agreement for an intelligent destination of some pillars. According to Santos et. al. (2021), Caldas Novas and Rio Quente need joint actions to improve tourism in these regions, not least because these cities have a range of tourist practices, where they attract a lot of tourists, therefore, to integrate this mission, it is necessary to have knowledge and a relationship of planning, private and public partnerships, respecting the difference of these places, however, these regions list a great need for conservation so that there is a positive potential in the results of economic growth.

In the following question, we asked if the inn participated in any project with the tourism department in the years 2015 to 2020 and, as in the answers given, we can verify that only one inn stated that it had participated.

In line with the answers, “the collective participation in the formulation of plans and projects contributes to the strengthening of local development, resulting in benefits for all involved”

(TURISMO EM FOCO, 2019, p. 21), in which it brings the prospect of reducing inequalities for a search for economic and social equity.

Continuing the next question asked how often this inn had participated during the period from 2015 to 2020, in response, only once.

In view of this, Santos et. al., (2020) explains that, the active participation of the inns in the execution of tourist projects, contributes to local development, through exchange of experiences and sharing of knowledge, since, designing strategies will result in the solution of complexities and local needs that establish in favor of the receiving community which, in turn, begins to create a tourist/visitor relationship as a participatory process in tourism planning.

It was also asked if the inn had already carried out any evaluation regarding the performance of the employees and as a response given by the participants it was verified that 2 (two) stated that they had already carried out an evaluation and 11 (eleven) stated that they had not carried out any

performance evaluation.

Through these responses, Carvalho (2012) emphasizes that evaluating the performance of employees is to bring the best way to know their professional profile, understand their potential and identify their possible difficulties, intended to improve productivity and results to be achieved. This is because these assessment techniques are essential not only for performance, but also to encourage collaboration and teamwork.

In the following question, it was asked if they had already carried out any training with the employees and in the answers given, it was observed that 3 (three) inns stated that they had carried out training, while 10 (ten) stated that they had not carried out training.

According to Silva Barreto; Albuquerque; Medeiros (2014) the training process with employees is to bring their preparation, aiming to deal with all the conditions involved in the execution of activities, therefore, training becomes fundamental for the internal segments of the place, as well as, a correct functioning and more assertive, because it is through these strategies that the demands and expectations are aligned to integrate all involved.

To complement the questioning, it was asked how often the inn conducts training with employees and the answers are shown in the chart below.

Graph Frequency of training with employees of the inns of Caldas Novas in the year 2022

Source: Data from the researcher (2022).

Observing the answers in the graph above, Carvalho (2012) explains that employee training must be frequent, due to the strategies that establish the important transmission of a culture of values, local politics and philosophy. Therefore, employees become aware of what is expected, resulting in improved performance, in addition to avoiding behaviors that may influence the organization. Therefore, there is an objective listed in the training that, in turn, establishes a single purpose of an efficient operation.

In the following, the participants were asked if they knew about the 360-degree assessment and it was verified that none of the participants was aware of such an assessment.

According to Silva Barreto; Albuquerque; Medeiros (2014) when defining evaluation as an instrument that can be used in employee management, aiming to monitor team or individual performance. This tool is able to analyze various segments, in order to create strategies that are capable of developing the engagement, productivity and motivation of local professionals.

It was asked how the management of the inn would define the Environment in Novas Caldas and the answers about the definitions about the management of the inn and the Environment in Caldas Novas, proved to be blunt with the actions, and there are other issues that had the slightest consideration, the need to comply with legislation, preservation and tourist activities.

According to Sartori et. al. (2014), the environment in Novas Caldas is hampered by the lack of political interest, which is a challenge that is posed to public authorities, whatever the project or program to be applied, the municipality needs sustainable development. For that, the functions of the local ecosystem, in a renewable way, must count on the contribution in the capacity of produced wealth, social balance, among other aspects that are necessary to bring social harmony. In the subsequent question, they were asked what were the difficulties encountered in maintaining the preservation of the local environment and the

answers were presented that the dissatisfaction with garbage collection as a higher priority in the difficulties, stating that the problems of Caldas Novas are related to human action, inserting this in a complex condition that needs to be reviewed through interventions or strategies, in order to further degrade the natural resources of this municipality.

According to Sousa; Barbosa (2008), the maintenance and prevention of the environment has been carried out by several public managers, in which the difficulties give more attention to those environmental complexities, starting to directly compromise the quality of life of the people of this municipality, such as the related selective collections, for example. However, depending on this local reality and the perception of each citizen, there are other issues that may be more relevant in this city, which is human awareness.

CONCLUSION

The study found that the city of Caldas Novas had a significant advance in complexity in environmental management, which is why local activities imply in the face of the natural resources of this region, implying that the management of this municipality presents fragility that impacts on the implementations and inspections of environmental policies. Noting that the municipal bodies that make up this region guide such procedures that regulate protection and prevention, however, according to economic speed, it negatively reflects several sectors, including inns and hotels.

When looking at numbers obtained from the municipal management of the environment and water resources, especially in the period between 2015-2020, there is slight progress in decision-making aimed at making public authorities available to obtain better results in managing the environment environment.

Therefore, it was observed that, during the research of theoretical references, the tourist activities of Caldas Novas, are users of thermal waters which, in turn, have several licenses that meet the dictates of legislation, Resolutions, among other

legal devices. It is noticed that there is a list of instruments that are referred to the framework of economic means that potentiate local pollution and that end up causing factors that significantly prove the environmental impact.

For all the above, it is concluded that the constant significant increase of visitors, in Caldas Novas, causes the inns to be overcrowded, overloading their basic services, noting that this floating population starts to provide an increase in demand that results in the local degradation. However, it is summarized that tourist activities directly affect this municipality, harming the daily lives of residents of this city, considering that the management of these establishments is primarily responsible for negative experiences in this territory.

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**Av. Pastor Martin Luther King Júnior,
126 (Torre 2000 Sala 104)
Del Castilho
Rio de Janeiro - RJ - Brasil
CEP 20765-971
TEL: +55 (21) 3490-5511**

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